

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION PROGRAM

MICHELLE PUNONGBAYAN OCHOA

**A DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF C4D MODEL IN CSR COMMUNICATION
– THE AMWAY PHILIPPINES “ONE BY ONE CAMPAIGN FOR CHILDREN”
CASE STUDY**

Thesis Adviser:

MELINDA DP BANDALARIA, Ph.D.

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

May 15, 2018

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR and any contractual obligations

Invention (I)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Publication (P)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Confidential (C)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Free (F)	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

Student's signature: SGD. Michelle Punongbayan Ochoa

Thesis adviser's signature:

University Permission Page

I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this thesis in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a) To upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and
- b) To publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and
- c) To give open access to the above-mentioned work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provisions of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.

SGD. MICHELLE PUNONGBAYAN OCHOA

May 15, 2018

Acceptance Page

This Master's Thesis titled A Descriptive Analysis of C4D Model in CSR Communication - The Amway Philippines "One by One Campaign for Children" Case Study is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication.

MELINDA DP. BANDALARIA, Ph.D.
Chair, Thesis Committee

May 15, 2018
(Date)

ALEXANDER G. FLOR, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Committee

May 15, 2018
(Date)

BENJAMINA PAULA FLOR, Ph.D.
Member, Thesis Committee

May 15, 2018
(Date)

ALEXANDER G. FLOR, Ph.D.
Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

May 15, 2018
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

The author, Michelle Punongbayan Ochoa, was born in Pasig City (then part of Rizal Province), on August 3, 1973 and currently residing in Jacksonville, Florida, U.S.A. The eldest daughter of Ester Landas Tampoc, and the late Architect Isabelo Manimtim Punongbayan.

She took her elementary education at a Catholic school, La Immaculada Concepcion School, and her secondary education at Rizal High School, was part of the pilot class. She graduated with awards as the school's Essayist of the year in 1989 to 1990, and the Associate Editor of The Rizalian, the school's official organization and newsletter. In the midst of struggling to finish her education, she benefited from a scholarship given by The Rotary Club of Pasig which sustained her high school education. She pursued her Bachelor's Degree in Journalism at the University of Santo Tomas and was the Assistant Literary Editor of The Flame, official magazine of the Faculty of Arts and Letters, while writing freelance. As a young mother when she was 18, her daughter Nadine Camille was her elixir of hope. She wore different hats in various private multinational corporations namely Dun & Bradstreet Philippines, Century Canning Corporation, Jollibee Food Corporations, and Amway Philippines L.L.C., an affiliate of Altacor and Amway's Global Headquarters in Michigan, U.S.A. Her recent job as a Corporate Affairs and Executive Officer of Amway Philippines allowed her to lead several corporate social responsibility projects under the company's "One by One Campaign for Children" where she extensively applied communication concepts from her Development Communication subjects in UPOU.

Michelle Punongbayan Ochoa

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researcher would like to thank the following people who had been instrumental in the completion of this study:

To Dr. Melinda DP. Bandalaria for her guidance and her valuable insights and suggestions to help put focus on the study with her knowledge and expertise shared on the topic of communications and its application in CSR;

To Dr. Benjamina Paula Flor, and Dr. Alexander Flor for the inspiration to complete this course, and patience in making suggestions to improve the study;

To Amway Philippines L.L.C. management team, employees, distributors who relentlessly supported the campaign and the communities that needed help. To the Department of Education and ASP partners;

To the researcher's parents, Ester and the late Isabelo Punongbayan, Jr., husband Arthur, daughter Nadine Ochoa, and friends who provided encouragement to finish this course and those who believed in her dream to help bring change in the lives of others. The author also acknowledges her grandparents – Loreto and Cesar Landas who provided the inspiration for her to finish her education.

Most importantly, the highest gratitude to God who has been a witness to the challenges and struggles that were part of the researcher's life and career, and for giving her the wisdom to understand her limitations and accept her gifts as tools to empower other people.

Dedicated to:

The University of the Philippines Open University community, the researcher's family, friends, Amway Philippines Global, Amway Philippines L.L.C. for ten years of giving the opportunity to serve, and to God almighty for the courage to finish and complete this journey towards wholeness.

Table of Contents

TITLE PAGE	i
ACCEPTANCE PAGE	ii
BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH.....	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
DEDICATION	vi
ABSTRACT	1
CHAPTER I	5
INTRODUCTION.....	5
Background and Rationale of the Study.....	5
Statement of the Problem.....	8
Objectives of the Study	16
Significance of the Study.....	17
Scope and Limitations of the Study	18
CHAPTER II	20
REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	20
Theoretical Framework.....	34
Conceptual Framework	38
Chapter III	44

METHODOLOGY.....	44
CHAPTER IV.....	46
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	46
CHAPTER V.....	60
SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	61
Summary.....	61
Conclusion.....	68
Recommendations	69
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	78
List of Appendices	
APPENDIX A.....	80
Partnership Certificates	
Volunteers in Action	
APPENDIX B.....	82
Library Infrastructures	
Photos of activities	
APPENDIX C	84
Yolanda Outreach	
APPENDIX D	85
Brigada Eskwela photos	
APPENDIX E.....	86
Brigada Eskwela Photo 2	

APPENDIX G

APPENDIX F 87

Communication Materials for CSR Tie-Ups with PR and Marketing

APPENDIX H 89

APPENDIX I 111

APPENDIX J 122

APPENDIX K 123

ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) communication happens extensively during project implementation, across various levels, and between various stakeholders. The importance of communicating the message and intention of the company is vital to the achievement of sustainable goals for individuals and communities that benefit from such initiatives. Amway Philippines' "One by One Campaign for Children" is a global campaign supporting various children's causes worldwide. In the Philippines, the program is aimed at SDG 4, or supporting quality education through a values-laden literacy through storytelling campaign under the Department of Education's Adopt-A-School Program (ASP). It was proven that in all locations where the Amway business operates, public school partners and students benefited from library renovations and other related support activities, which resulted in a sustainable relationship through effective communication and technology, such as email communication, social media channels, that mobilized volunteers across the organization.

Morsing and Schultz (2006), noted that engagement in present times requires a more sophisticated and ongoing stakeholder awareness and more focused CSR communication strategies than previously. This solidifies the need to make a CSR communication platform as that is "sustainable" and more attuned to the needs of various stakeholders. The element of "sustainability", makes the Amway Philippines One by One Campaign a movement to uplift the lives of its beneficiaries. The communication for development (C4D) model, allows the campaign to tap into various forms of communication, and utilize the technology that allows the implementation on a global and affiliate level. The barriers of distance and time is no longer a challenge since the

messaging tools are freely utilized using email, social media channels, and the Amway web-based resources such as blogs, microsites, and websites. Feedback is gathered, and dialogues are made to open up the communication lines either personally or through technology-aided communication.

With the vision to help children live better lives, Amway employees and partners donated volunteer hours. They went beyond helping schools but also communities with the commitment to become responsible for their respective areas. Thus, bringing small change to one child, one school, one community at a time. Most corporate entities perform philanthropy as an act of “giving back” to communities, sometimes with the consideration of proximity (if the area of the project is their place of business) or for any valid social cause. Katherine V. Smith, Executive Director of Boston College, in the paper Corporate Citizenship, Five Areas for Action, raised the question of whether corporations are doing enough to create the kind of communities they intend to do business in, and, moreover, a world that people would like to live in, maybe since CSR is constantly hounded with the double standard of being a business instrument, more than a tool for social change. However, this study would like to focus more on the positive benefits to society that such collective corporate initiatives can derive. For a moment, keep an open mind on the negative ones like corruption, and personal gains without being judgmental. Instead, the researcher would like to illustrate how change and development may be gained through effective CSR communication.

As of 2015 data, the private sector's contribution to education support projects, combining infrastructure and non-infrastructure projects, amounts to about 6 billion pesos, which is outside of the Department of Education Budget (sourced from a direct interview

of ASP partners, 2016). Such donations and pledges gave way to achieving quality education in the Philippines amidst the government's budget gap.

In the Philippines, where most of the places where Amway conducts its CSR campaign are separated by geographical barriers, technology has helped bridge the communication gap. Various teams were provided with the same communication kits during specific projects under the literacy campaign. They were given the same budget allocation as their counterparts from their headquarters in Manila. One message works for all beneficiary schools in different communities. It is all aimed at a single objective of providing these schools with resources under the literacy campaign that was launched in 2004.

Through a recently conducted FGD in 2016 and a survey in 2017, the researcher gathered insights as to how effective the communicated message of companies like Amway Philippines, through their CSR projects under the One by One Campaign for Children, drew action that has stirred positive change and brought development in the communities where they operate. A measurement of whether the local campaign was communicated effectively and if the key message is aligned with the company's values (of Helping People Live Better Lives) is also discussed with volunteer employees. It also aims to measure the level of confidence (behavioral factors and behavioral changes like having ownership of their community activities) of the volunteer in the campaign projects.

Amway uses the C4D model of communication. As a result, six schools benefited, and several communities responded to it as a collective action of participants, as evidenced in the annual run activity. This only proves that CSR, if at all construed as a

marketing approach, is “marketing with a soul”, that is - one that at least addresses a societal concern. Erstwhile, the fuel that makes CSR work is communication, and its by-product is ultimately- the development of individuals and society.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, information communication technologies for development, ICT4D, CSR, social marketing, social mobilization, CSR for development

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background and Rationale of the Study

CSR Communication - When the Key Message Creates Action

Gandhi has faith in humanity and the goodness of the human soul. He calls himself a soldier of peace and believes in the power of the “minority soul.” One person uplifts others, whose efforts combined with other individuals create a powerful force for social good. Imagine if more Gandhi’s were inside us, more individuals moving as a force for good. How about a whole institution of heroic private citizens changing other people’s situation? This is what’s illustrated in Corporate Social Responsibility Projects. Powerful communication can help bring the message of “doing good” for society and can propel small steps that can bring social change. When private individuals collectively become involved in the task of community development, the results can be beneficial.

Amway’s mission and vision are to “Help People Live Better Lives.” In its broad sense, their CSR campaign could be narrowed down to a specific goal to address a unique need in every affiliate country. The keywords used are “help,” “people,” and “better lives” as a result. The same operational values embedded in the direct selling business they offer, is the concept of opening opportunities to all people, regardless of their race, origins, ethnic or cultural beliefs, as long as they work hard for it. However, the direct selling business is shrouded with doubt as the proliferation of fly-by-night schemes from

some industry members makes it twice as challenging for Amway and other industry-compliant corporations to create a positive image.

In Velasco et al. 1999, *Social Marketing and Social Mobilization for Development*, the difference between social marketing and commercial marketing was broadly discussed. Lee and Kotler (2011) proposed a 9-step guide question, while Duxbury presented his eight key steps, giving us insight into how the social marketing environment is best described. The most important question perhaps brings us to “what social issue is addressed” and what benefits from social marketing. In *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)* is a practice that derives its effectiveness through various activities and is largely influenced by stakeholder relationships and how the private individual or corporation can “market” a social good based on their chosen goals and objectives. Some practices in social marketing are also applicable in implementing CSR activities. Some metrics have been made to measure the results of such initiatives. Still, the scholarly approach to measuring the results tells us to veer away from pitfalls like unrealistic objectives or barriers that will keep us from getting insights on data like general awareness or feelings (Bandalaria, 2014), or double-barreled objectives. The foreseen negative views about public and private partnerships depicted as a breeding ground for societal ills like corruption and self-serving motivations of corporations became this paper's purpose. The researcher intends to study how communication exists between the partners and stakeholders and how social issues are addressed as a result of social mobilization in CSR, which further help achieves development.

Amway Philippines is the largest direct selling company globally, with global sales of 8.8 billion in FY 2016-2017 (Direct Selling News 2017, by the data, by the numbers.)

They have also been known and perceived as providers of high-quality products (like health supplements, beauty, personal care, agriculture, and homecare) that are environmentally friendly and backed by their own research facilities, the name Amway is somehow given the identity as a prestige brand. This puts them as a brand that is “aspirational” or “inspirational” for the users.

It could also suggest the product's value and potential for start-up entrepreneurs. The audience or target market usually belongs to the A and B market, and recently the “C” market also finds affinity in some product innovations (recently, their local coffee brand “Achievers,” which was manufactured by Figaro, a known Filipino coffee expert coffee company, and Miyu, a beauty brand launched in 2016 for Gen Y market). Yet, in all of these complexities of the business, the need to extend itself towards community work has always been imprinted in the corporate mission and vision and has not stopped them from looking into the need to expand their corporate imprint in places where help is needed.

The Amway affiliate office in the Philippines comprises only more or less 70 employees and a distributor base of 45,000 to 65,000 distributors nationwide (2004-2016 data.) This, perhaps, is the company’s greatest asset, its people. The same people diligently volunteer to help their communities with minimal resources. One would imagine why a company would need to invest in the social good, yet the reasons perhaps are relevant to their company mission and vision of “Helping People Live Better Lives.”

Debunking the Negative Image of CSR - When the Good Offsets the Bad

Is CSR a practice that is shrouded with the company's personal agenda, wrapped in a blanket of good deeds as often perceived? Is this a necessary bargain between

private entities to harness the opportunity for hidden objectives to promote, protect, market their corporate identities? How about if we looked beyond this and focus on how CSR campaigns can change the lives of people for better? How can communication make helping other people attractive and relevant to this generation? Is CSR more than just a marketing scheme? Or is it all about mobilizing people for the common good that makes CSR an acceptable tool to achieve development?

More than this, we as development communicators can open our doors to study the communication process between stakeholders closely study CSR from a grounded, level-headed perspective.

In the meantime, we will set aside interests and evaluate how effective communication process is crucial to the delivery of social good.

Statement of the Problem

The challenge of providing adequate resources to sustain a growing population of students, and the mandate to make affordable free quality education is a huge challenge that DepEd faces each year.

According to an article from SunStar Manila (online version), based on the Annual Poverty Indicator Survey (APIS) some 3.8 million Filipino youth ages ranging from 6 to 24 years, are out of school youth. APIS is a nationwide survey that represents the profile of Filipino families and their living conditions. UNESCO data shows that there are approximately 2 million Pre-Primary students and 13 million Primary students alone. Data also shows that there is an approximate 25% decline on the survival rate of finishing the last grade of primary education, which is 75% from 100% intake in 2013. Although literacy

rate is high at 98% for ages 15 and up, the government expenditure for education is a mere 2.6% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from 2007 to 2009. Given this trend, the need to support the ballooning population of 100 million Filipinos would take more than government action. This entails a joint commitment from both the private sector and the government.

Moreover, with the implementation of the K to 12 educational system in 2012, which aligns the Philippine Educational System parallel to international standards in education (in terms of length of time spent and under a specialized skills-based curriculum), DepEd needs to secure a bigger budget on top of its current allocation from the annual national budget to transition to this new educational system.

K to 12 holds the promise to position the Philippines at par with its counterparts in South East Asia and the rest of the world. Three years after its implementation, we can hope that we are now ready to launch a new generation of graduates who are highly competent based on international standards.

As for Amway, it has chosen to be a champion for quality education. It chose DepEd as a local partner because of the following reasons: one, education is important for Filipinos and their families, and is perceived as a way to combat poverty; secondly, the government is a good channel to reach the community and Amway has several locations nationwide where public schools are abundant and in need of support. Although the partnership is well defined by a Memorandum of Understanding that allows the company to manage its resources based on a signed agreement (MOU), and everything is ideally transparent between partners including budget and implementation, this is not

the sole ingredient that will make implementation a success. Communicating with partners and stakeholders does.

Likewise, the researcher aims to discuss the following:

1. How does CSR Communication drive action and create impact in the lives of various stakeholders and partners?

2. Can we categorize CSR Communication as a form of Communication for Development or C4D?

3. How can communication (C4D) help hasten interaction within a CSR partnership which eventually leads to development? How is this applied in Amway's CSR campaign?

4. What are the types of communication used between CSR participants and partners and how does it help put the expectations of all stakeholders into account?

5. How does the program message affect the level of participation of volunteers?

What transpires in a CSR Project and how are the needs of both the corporation and the beneficiaries met using C4D Tools? What communication processes are used and how do these methods and mediums of communication facilitate the process of development in the lives of the beneficiaries?

Experience with social mobilization, social marketing and community participation in developing countries has stirred a good deal of critical thinking and writing on operational and ethical issues during the last two decades. There is a myriad of things to

consider, such as how to sustain programs, institutionalize skills and replicate successes. What management methods are most appropriate and what is the best personnel mix when forming a program team? Which are the best research methods to employ in different situations? How should products and services be positioned? And, in what circumstances is it most appropriate to employ social marketing, social mobilization or full-scale community participation where the community is involved in choosing and prioritizing problems to solve? (McKee, 2004, *Social Mobilization and Social Marketing in Developing Communities: Lessons for Communicators*) In the same publication, McKee (2004) in Chapter 5 illustrates the various facets of Social Mobilization and Community participation in developing country settings. There are many concerns hounding the true purpose of CSR and social marketing and how these constitute “the common good”.

These issues are on top of the concern on how CSR and social mobilization can be planned, instituted and sustained. During the planning stage until implementation of CSR projects, communication is an indispensable tool.

It is also very important in delivering the message and managing expectations of all stakeholders, such that documenting and distributing these would require key messaging tools and technology to create a bigger impact.

In 2013, during the Amway One by One Campaign 10th Year Anniversary, Amway headquarters in Michigan and their local counterparts created an event in November 20 which coincides with the world volunteer month, November. Massive web-based content and microsites were created to amplify the message and intent to help 10,000 children worldwide. However, the message was clear that all efforts, no matter how small the

magnitude of the implementation, contributes to a greater whole - the sum of all the parts which is, to help people live better lives.

From the perspective of the beneficiaries of the campaign, this would mean an opportunity to change their current situation. For the company, it was their chance to show their responsibility as part of the direct selling industry which is has been subjected to industry and government related issues.

For the employees, it was the chance to do something big for other people who may need it. The many dimensions of CSR are addressed and communicated to various audiences - the company, the employees, the beneficiaries, the government and the rest of the world.

The fine line between CSR, social mobilization, community participation is one that intersects with one another such that the concepts seem to overlap. More so, the communication process that occur within these practices are complexly interrelated that it is inevitable not to discuss CSR without discussing linkages to social mobilization and community participation, and talk about community goals, addressing needs, and driving resources to achieve action and desired social transformation and development.

Corporate Social Responsibility is a very controversial practice, and in fact represents two sides of a coin, because of the perceived duality of purpose, as both a bringer of benefit to beneficiaries of corporations, and the alleged self-serving motives of the corporation or private institution (donor and beneficiary relationship).

This paper was written not to define CSR's legitimacy as a practice or field of study, but to understand the importance of the communication process between stakeholders

and the success of the project. In particular, the writer of this thesis seeks to describe in detail communication methods and theories in relation to the achievement of goals (speed of delivery, social mobilization of volunteers and participants, and the interaction process inside and outside the organization or company.)

A case study of Amway Philippines L.L.C.s “One by One Campaign” will be used as a benchmark for all presented communication materials used, including the interactions with stakeholders (Department of Education, various beneficiary schools, Amway employees, and Amway Distributors.)

The study aims to illustrate the different means of communication used (including traditional methods like written materials, i.e. memorandum of understanding, invitation letters, to modern approaches like electronic mails, social media, websites, e-news, and how these are extensively used in the staging of recognition events, fund raising activities, and eventually - the achievement of the CSR goal which is to deliver expectations for all stakeholders.

In Morsing and Schultz (2006), key messages about corporate ethical and socially responsible initiatives are likely to evoke strong and often positive reactions among stakeholders. In the same discussion, they mentioned that research has even pointed out the business benefits of the internal and external communication of corporate social responsibility (CSR) efforts (citing Maignan et.al, 1999). Morsing and Schultz also mentioned that while CSR reflects the status and activities with respect to the positive corporate virtues (e.g. Johnson & Johnson, The Body Shop, Patagonia) this they say, also attracted critical attention to the organization’s position and true intentions with

respect to the expected social benefits of the activities and initiatives of companies to help society and reveals their ethical and social ambition. Sometimes, companies who help social causes are often targets of doubts and are accused of possibly hiding something behind their intentions.

Such dynamic communication process is involved in supporting countless development goals.

This discussion aims to zoom-in on Sustainable Development Goal SDG 4, which is the desired end result of interactions in the sample CSR campaign mentioned. Amway's CSR project, One by One Campaign for children, specifically those under the Public and Private Partnerships (PPPs) and is part of the Department of Education's "Adopt-A-School Program" (ASP), a campaign that gathers support from private entities and corporations who implement Corporate Social Responsibility Projects (CSR), have been in place as part of the Department of Education's mechanism to sustain the standard education platform (K to 12) and likewise a solution to address the gap in the national budget for education. This also poses a need to communicate with various stakeholders and applying business communication between Amway management and CSR lead and government, to as basic as community conversations with participants (teachers, employees, distributors of Amway).

The communication method used would vary depending on what is needed, and how fast these forms of communication can be transferred and decoded for certain audiences in the partnership.

Objectives of the Study

1. The researcher will focus on documenting how the communication process happens in a CSR Campaign, particularly under the Amway Philippines L.L.C. CSR project “One by One Campaign” and illustrate how C4D is used in Social Mobilization for CSR and identify the various C4D communication tools, traditional and modern means of interactions used in a CSR Campaign to achieve the goals of both the corporation and the beneficiaries.
2. In particular, the researcher will strive to show in details how communication transpires between partners under Amway’s CSR Projects using the C4D matrix and the suggested fifth element, “replication and sustainability” (see page 15, C4D Conceptual framework) as an important practice in CSR communications and its desirable effect towards development (forms of communication extensively used, e.g. letters, emails, verbal communication, ICT used like computers, computer applications, social media platforms (FB and Web) and how these help ease the communication process in many locations nationwide.

For the company to deliver their CSR thrust, it interacts with its stakeholders from the government (DepED and LGUs), organizations (partners like Museo Pambata, and their internal suppliers, media etc.), internal customers (employees and distributors), and their public.

Aligned with the company’s mission and vision of “Helping People Live Better Lives”, the message aims to promote “well-being” of people, whether economic, social,

or personal well-being. Today, as the concept of helping evolves, the message also changes from a “child-oriented campaign” to more of “community”, “social” and “environmental” in purpose.

Still anchored on SGD2, the 2016-2017 global campaign of Amway deals with addressing the worldwide malnutrition problem through their “Little Bits, Power of 5” project. This is an offshoot of the UNICEF research findings that “global undernutrition contributes to nearly half of all deaths of children under 5” and is prevalent in Asia and Africa (see <https://powerof5.nutrilite.com>.)

As of 2016, there were ongoing talks to implement this project as well in the Philippines Market. The need to partner with a local feeding program was also a challenge in the affiliate because of the limited manpower to oversee a massive implementation, that a decision was made to retain the original thrust of the campaign which is literacy and education, Moving forward, Amway Philippines affiliate supported SDG4 or Quality Education through their partnership with DepEd (partners since 2004), which the local management decided to sustain due to the recent implementation of the K to 12 education which puts the Philippines at the forefront of a major step to upgrade its educational system based on international standards.

Significance of the Study

According to the World Health Organization Publication Communication for Behavioral Impact (COMBI), Communication for Development (C4D) is defined as listening, building trust, sharing knowledge and skills, building policies, debating and learning for sustained and meaningful change. Erstwhile, McKee (1992) defines advocacy as the organization of information into an argument to be communicated through various interpersonal and media channels with a view of gaining political and social leadership acceptance and preparing society for a particular development program. It is persuasive communication against an issue or raising a concern.

Communication has always been an important tool in all human interactions. In its more sublime purpose, it helps translate the message of intent in advocacy projects and participatory development. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is anchored on one or many related projects where communication is vital in order to plan, implement, gain support of decision makers, and sustain partnerships made. The communication necessary to spur development is best described by Flor (2007, Development Communication Praxis), as an independent discipline that does not just aid the projects that require it. It is the Fifth Theory of the Press. This brings about the realization of man's potential (Gandhi, Seers, Lasswell, Lerner, Freire, Schramm and Quebral), with the sole purpose of social transformation, the fulfillment of basic needs, as used by the government, organizations, religious orders, grassroots organizations et al.

In the case of Amway and its One by One campaign, the CSR thrust originally was child-focused, then this expanded through the years as they saw the need to address other community, social and environmental concerns.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study will focus on the local campaign of Amway in the Philippines, and in particular, the literacy campaign under the Department of Education's Adopt-A-School Program (ASP), the storytelling caravan, DEPED's "Brigada Eskwela", and the annual Amway 1K Run which is a hybrid Marketing and CSR event. The FGD conducted is done through the participation of 10 respondents (7 of 20 employees who are based in Makati Amway Headquarters and of 3 provincial based employees) who are either CSR team leaders or volunteers who have joined any literary campaign caravan, or either have donated to the campaign, or have directly received information and communication about the campaign. Highlights on offline interviews of major participants like school coordinators and principals, Amway management, and originators of the communication, and program officer will be included. Results of the three major projects will also be highlighted and the communication tools used described and analyzed.

This research likewise aims to establish the following hypotheses:

1. H1 - Development results from CSR initiatives, and communication for development (C4D) is the discipline that makes the CSR Program like Amway's One by One Campaign, achieve its end goal which is to uplift the individual and society towards development.

2. H2 - CSR activities are enhanced by using communication tools for social mobilization and through emotional messaging approaches.

3. H3 - Communication for Development (C4D) is an effective way to manage the expectations most CSR campaigns such as Amway's One by One Campaign for Children and puts more emphasis on the result rather than personal gain or return of investments (ROI.) The ROI of CSR is measured by the favorability rates from its internal and external customers.

4. H4 - Private Corporations and Individuals are powerful participants in the development process. Possibly, an underestimated resource in the development process and nation building. CSR can intermarry with Development Communication in principle.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Defining CSR as a Legitimate Development Activity

Leslie Lenkowsky (2011, quoted by Ken Allen, 2012, in “The Big Tent, Corporate Volunteering in The Global Age) in his memorial to the late Robert Payton, a pioneer in education for philanthropy, wrote that Payton firmly held that “practice was overwhelming theory” and it was “reducing education to training”.

He further stressed that something similar might be said about Corporate Volunteering or Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), that “practice overwhelmed crucial thought.”

Allen (2012) mentioned the need to be “sensitive to the why’s and the how’s of volunteering and that there must create a framework of understanding on both the concepts and the practice”, notwithstanding the perceived good effects, but also to have a critical view of its implications Allen also centers on the “spirituality” of the act of volunteering and mentions this dimension is not necessarily “religious” but more of an offshoot of a need to bring to fruition the development needed, and “distribute” the power in society and “enable” those who lack it.

Furthermore, he said that CSR is more of an “inspiring practice” and not just a “best practice of a company or institution who engages in it.” The reason we need to define CSR and its true dimension in the development process, is because this is necessary to validate the importance of CSR in the development process of a country, in

relation to how we can apply development communication and technology (C4D) as a tool to accomplish the intended “change” or “improvement” in the lives of people who are recipients and beneficiaries of these CSR projects. Probably, this would be justifying the means to an end, provided that the intent is clearly specified as beneficial to the intended or target audience.

In order to do this, we must first set aside the intention to criticize CSR as a practice and deal with it in the proper forum and focus on its potential, and perhaps elevate it as a development activity, instead of just a company initiative. Although in Development Communication, it is forbidden to do manipulative advertising (Flor,2007), which is somehow done in CSR, and this poses the conflicting views of both practices. Somehow, the researcher hopes to contest this because by nature, development communication and its end goal which is “development” is likewise an end result of CSR. In a nutshell, CSR is also a married discipline with DEVCOM, taking into account the purpose of which is to “uplift human condition and address societal concern” (Quebral). Maybe the rationale to this is that corporations and private entities too, are part of this society and have the same responsibility in helping address developmental problems. Instead, veering away from a critique of CSR would make it more objective for the discussion of how communication in a CSR setting would lead to development of the participants - a means to a sublime end. For after all, the distribution of power and wealth in underdeveloped countries or developing nations is a reality that cannot be escaped. If we let those with the resources and power to empower the weak, then, it is an act of uplifting of the powerless and the marginalized poor, still. And the spirit of Development Communication will not just be a concept that is held in a limbo or utopia of being a mere discipline but a forgiving one as

well, that is open to take an experimental look into the untapped potential of CSR as an aligned discipline, but with a cautious and careful stance. Careful and cautious, because true CSR should be leaning towards working under the radar or unseen, except by the people who are participants and observers of the program, and is more focused on the positive change it brings.

As of September 2017, there are 120 companies and corporations who are partners of the Department of Education under the Adopt-A-School Program (ASP). One of the partners is Amway Philippines L.L.C. who is currently both an infrastructure and non-infrastructure donor with their literacy campaign through storytelling. Amway adopts a school in near every Amway Distribution Center, builds or renovates an existing library, donates books and conducts regular storytelling activities and scheduled feeding programs in six adopted schools nationwide.

In conducting their relationship building with the government, the school representatives, parents volunteers, LGUs, their employee and distributor volunteers, the company has to align and communicate their message and intent, in accordance with the company's mission and vision, while taking into consideration the needs of the various stakeholders. Such communication process happens in all levels of the organization and across their vital audiences - their internal customers (employees and distributors) and the public they wish to reach.

What's in a Name? Finding a Cause and Communicating the Message

Amway's One by One Campaign for Children is a global initiative launched in 2003 in various affiliates under the Michigan-based direct selling company, Amway Global Corporation and Alticor. Anchored on the company's mission and vision of helping children worldwide to live better lives, the founders of Amway, Rich DeVos and Jay Van Andel, made sure that their legacy of kindness is shared in places where their business operates. Amway now has over 100 affiliates globally, and in all these affiliates, a community-oriented project to help initially children, and eventually sustained various causes, including those that needed developmental support for individuals and communities, which is not limited to societal, educational, medical, economic, but also include environmental campaigns. The company (Amway) was built on four pillars - "Freedom, Family, Hope and Rewards".

Through the values instilled in each pillar, affiliates choose to support their cause based on the present needs of their community. The key message of the name however is "children" and how the company aims to help as many as they can, "one child at a time" in places where they operate. In over 80 affiliate offices worldwide, the campaign has gained a good following from employees, distributors and their communities and gathers its strength from its main resource which is their workforce.

Since then, the company was able to mobilize more than 10,000 million volunteers worldwide (2013), and has contributed over 10 million US Dollars to the cause. Although the campaign may differ from one country to another, the centrality of its focus is on family, community, children, health, and helping people.

The campaign name “One by One for Children” is intrinsically a tool to stir concern about children, their situation, and the conditions of the communities they belong to. Children, being the most fragile and vulnerable members of society, and one that are sometimes subjected to human rights violation in some countries, are the same children who are seen as the potential future of any country, whether developed or underdeveloped. In choosing this name, a strong message and a call to action is made. The rights and protection of children is in fact a global concern, and one that demands quick and swift action.

Flor (2007) cited the works of Lasswell, Lerner, and Schramm’s writings as the origins of communication’s role in the socio-political frameworks, and puts it in the heart of social transformation. He said that communication should be achieved swiftly to achieve societal development (also in Quebral.)

Each time Amway and its employees adopt one school, this ensures that some 600 to 2,000 students, depending on the size of the school population, will benefit from a conducive library facility, access to free educational materials such as books and references, and valuable interaction with volunteers, who believe in the power of values education, culture, and education.

Defining Communication for Development (C4D) as the Key Driver and Discipline Applied in Amway's One by One Campaign CSR Program

In the Philippines, "One by One Campaign for Children" (the original campaign name, 2003) was launched through an initial partnership with the Association De Damas de Filipinas, a Catholic orphanage in Manila. During the launch, the orphans were sponsored to a field trip with employees of the company to the Enchanted Kingdom for a day to celebrate children's rights and to kick off the affiliate's CSR initiative in the Philippines. The following year, (2004), Amway Philippines, in partnership with the Department of Education, signed a memorandum of understanding (MOU), to adopt public schools in locations where Amway operates.

This began the journey of a private corporation (Amway Philippines) and the government (The Department of Education), alongside LGUs (local barangays) and communities of interest (teachers, parents, Amway employees, and other cause oriented children's rights advocacy groups like Museo Pambata, who worked together towards a sustainable literacy campaign.)

McKee 1992 defines advocacy as the organization of information into an argument to be communicated through various interpersonal and media channels with a view of gaining political and social leadership acceptance and preparing a society for a particular development program. The major audience of Amway's advocacy are leaders and funding agencies (Amway Management, Amway Global Headquarters), decision makers who have an upper hand as to the provision of funding is.

Meanwhile, political partners such as government and LGUs are also vital due to the fact that they provide the opportunity to reach the intended public (beneficiaries) through a policy-controlled environment (Public Private Partnership, ASP). Some form of regulation and norms do exist throughout the implementation of advocacy projects that the company should adhere to.

Interpersonal mediations occur between volunteers and school coordinators as a supplemental activity or a necessary reinforcement to achieve the end goal of the campaign.

According to UNICEF data on Philippines education, the primary school participation survival rate data is high at 90%, while a dip in the survival rate in primary school participation to the last primary grade is marked by just 75.8%. While enrollment rates are high, the assurance of a student moving up to the secondary level is diminished as they reach the last primary grade. Based on this, the need to sustain and support education remains a high priority.

Based on the Philippines Statistics Office data on education, although a steady growth on the number of elementary graduates year on year between 2000, 2007 and 2010, the rates of enrolled students in public schools are significantly high versus those enrolled in privately owned schools. The ratio of students (38 million in public schools against just 8 to 10 million students in private schools) rather gives us an insight on the weight of responsibility the government has in supporting the budget for education. Thus, due to this, companies like Amway Philippines decided to support DepEd's Adopt A

School Program under a Private Public Partnership (PPP.) This strengthened Amway Philippines' bid to help public schools in the places where they operate their business.

Each year, Amway adopted a school, renovates or builds a library, and used values-laden storytelling sessions conducted by Amway employees, distributors and their families (and with reference to one of Amway's core values pillar - "Family"). The need to communicate education as "children's rights" was successfully inculcated in the projects accomplished.

A total of seven schools were adopted through DepEd's "Adopt-A-School" Program in seven geographical locations nationwide (Makati City, Cagayan De Oro, Cebu, Urdaneta (beneficiary until 2015), Davao, Mandaluyong, and Manila). (See appendix A). Communication was extensively used to mobilize resources (manpower, funding, agreements, schedule et.al.) from concept to implementation. Various forms and channels of communication were used (letters, MOUs, emails, posters, text messaging, social media). Until recently in 2016, the global campaign was defined as more than a campaign for children's causes, and was named "One by One Campaign", to cover multiple sustainable causes, ranging from community to sustainable entrepreneurship.

It aims to empower the distributors and employees to achieve their fullest potential by becoming an essential part of their community, and also supports their individual causes as "champions of good".

In Ruiz, 2015, Integrative Framework to Understand How CSR Affects Customer Loyalty Through Identification, Emotions, and Satisfaction, it was mentioned that loyalty is the ultimate goal of a company and therefore he said that CSR image refers to the

perception and knowledge of a company's activities and status relating to its societal stakeholder obligations (citing He and Li, 2011).

A company's profitability is the main driver of business, more and more pressure on improving CSR image is gaining more following recently because as Ruiz further mentioned in his research, CSR image and customer loyalty are indirectly mediated by four affective variables: (1) customer company-identification, (2) customer emotions evoked by the company at institutional level, (3) customer emotions evoked by service performance, and (4) satisfaction. Thus, borrowing from this perspective, communicating the Corporate Social Responsibility Campaign objective plays an integral role in the whole relationship cycle between the company and its internal (employees) and external customers (volunteers and beneficiaries, prospective product users). The authenticity of the purpose is somehow mirrored in the way the program intention is communicated. The question of who the company intends to help, with what resources, and how and where this will be implemented is always strengthened by "why" the company is doing this initiative.

Review of Related Empirical Researches

In a Boston University publication by Mirvins, Googins, Capinha, Fombrun, Nielsen, Taciak and Young 2008, "Building Reputation Here, There and Everywhere; Worldwide Views on local impact of Corporate Social Responsibility", executive findings, authors noted the innate understanding in the business community that corporate reputations are valuable intangible assets, and key to building and protecting the company's success in its operating environment. The same research also stated that reputation is driven by engagement and CSR activities and this makes it important the

world's public. Likewise in the 2008 Global Pulse Report Survey, the top drivers of reputation are (1) ratings of product and services at 17.6 % of reputation index, (2) perception of the company's corporate citizenship at 16.3 %, (3) governance at 14.5 %, and (4) workplace practices and ethics at 14.6% which then place CSR as a driver of reputation in the public's mind. The reputation index first analysis of 600 global companies in 27 countries show that the highest-ranking countries are (1) Netherlands, Sweden, Norway, (2) India and South Africa because of good governance, (3) US companies based on all CSR dimensions. Amway Global being a US Based company is somehow influenced by this fact and is very concerned about their corporate citizenship being aligned with their business ethics.

Globally, Amway supports the fight against malnutrition (SDG2), and launched its Power of 5 Campaign as a fund drive to support the call for proper nutrition and a preventive measure to end the deaths of children under 5 years of age. This was implemented in various markets like Southeast Asia (Vietnam), Africa, and Latin America among others.

Locally, Amway partners with the Department of Education under the Adopt A School Program with education as its corporate citizenship thrust. With the recent implementation of K to 12 on May 15, 2013 as the Enhanced Basic Education Act was signed into law, the Philippines education sector begins to transition to an international standard education from its original 10-year primary and secondary educational program. However, given the limited budget of the Philippine Government, and a ballooning population of 100 million as of 2016.

Communicating the Good Through Marketing Related Activities:
Amway 1K Run - A Social Mobilization Event

After less than a decade after the One by One Campaign for Children was program was launched in the Philippines, a project called “Amway 1K Run” mobilized some 16,000 runners in 2011 to 2016 which sustained the programs funding on top of the company’s annual CSR budget, which supported the seven beneficiaries (literacy campaign, infrastructure projects for library renovations, and books) for some 10,000 children beneficiaries nationwide in 2013. (See Appendix B)

Growing the Circle of Goodness - Amway’s Disaster Response to Yolanda

Aside from these projects, employees of the company and its more than 40,000 distributors supported relief operations during calamities such as Typhoon Yolanda (International name “Haiyan”), which was considered one of the most devastating natural disasters in the world in terms of damage to lives and communities.

Only a few days after Yolanda, as an offshoot of a regional conference held in Amway’s Bangkok Headquarters where the Amway Philippines affiliate CSR lead person met with the Amway Global Marketing and CSR Team and South East Asia affiliate leads, the topic was raised immediately to the global executive office, who then expressed intentions to help Amway employees, distributors, and Typhoon Yolanda victims. Amway does not have physical presence in Tacloban where the disaster struck. However, they have distributors that were badly affected and displaced by the massive damage of Yolanda.

Its first recourse was to help its employees if any were affected, providing financial help to employees with affected families, then second, helping their distributors who were residents of the affected areas. Just a few days after the conference in Bangkok, Amway Global Headquarters, released an email that resulted to a donation of USD 100,000 which was channeled to a local partner, The Philippine Red Cross Organization. It was just the beginning.

On December 2013, South East Asia affiliates of the Amway Corporation managed to raise another over USD 60,000 which was also donated to PRC in another meeting with the organization's President, Dick Gordon and Amway executives.

In Michigan, where the story of how Yolanda wrought havoc in the lives of families who lost some less than 4,000 rendered missing or dead was communicated to Amway Headquarters, 10,000 hygiene kits were assembled and shipped to Manila through a partner "Care Organization" which then distributed these to victims of Yolanda. The kits contained Amway products like toothpaste, toothbrush, soap, shampoo, and implements like towels, and combs. Amway saw this as a mission to uplift the spirits of a community that was left in chaos after Yolanda. (See Appendix C)

In the Makati Amway Headquarters, and Cebu Headquarters of Amway, business owners/distributors, employees from rank and file to executives rolled up their sleeves to manage some 1,000 and 500 grocery packs respectively from the Makati and Cebu Relief Drive respectively, which were given to affected employees and distributors and their families. The relief operations had to be conducted by land to reach Tacloban (via RORO Transportation, and more than 8 hours travel) because the Tacloban airports were closed

and badly damaged. There were two relief drives done, one in December (3 months after Yolanda), and another in May 2013, where the company donated storytelling books to 11 schools during “Brigada Eskwela”. The donation of grocery bags and Amway products for teachers and those that were housed in a temporary center at Rizal Elementary School Tacloban also were some of the beneficiaries of the collective efforts of both distributors, employees and the company. (See Appendix D).

With a limited manpower to sustain all these activities (Amway has only 70 employees nationwide, 30 percent of which are Manila based), support was gathered from partners like DepEd (coordination), and its own distributors (Amway Business Owners, who were also affected by Yolanda, but were out of danger). Text messages were the main communication to key leaders in the location to gather information as to who were affected, and how broad the damage was.

Letters were drafted by DepEd to help public schools and manage the emotional damage on children who witnessed the calamity. In response, Amway, as a literacy advocate, donated storytelling books that teachers may use to entertain children during this emotional time. Two schools received Amway cleaning products that were used to wipe away the signs of Yolanda and prepare the rooms for the upcoming school year. (See Appendix D)

Allen (2012) also said that there can be no doubt that corporate volunteering, no matter how it is defined and executed, is one of the most significant volunteer assets available to help address our most important human, social and economic and environmental challenge. When businesses demonstrate the willingness to commit their

most important asset, their people, to this type of work, because he mentions that this shares their expertise and “people power” to communities worldwide.

CSR also needs to be seen in a different perspective. It also needs to be analyzed for the positive effects it gives to the participants (mainly the workers who implement) and the company that supports them. This is on top of the “good” it brings to society. Allen (2012) in the same publication, also stated that volunteering, no matter the setting in which it is done is not a value-free activity. He said that it embodies a world view, a spiritual dimension (although not necessarily religious), and often a political dimension. It is also a way of thinking and value how people can have the capacity to change and help others. There may be implications and underlying challenges, especially for the person who works to implement CSR projects, but he or she needs to transcend beyond these and should be open minded to succeed.

The main thrust of CSR however is how to mobilize resources and act as a bridge to accomplish the “good” for society’s sake. This is where communication plays a vital role. Barriers to communication are no longer that difficult in this age and time, that we as development communicators and CSR practitioners may now reap the benefits of technology in connecting people’s lives, seamlessly, and eradicate barriers of distance and time. It is also important in “creating the moment” (Allen, 2012) where the message is amplified and becomes a call to action.

Theoretical Framework

The researcher hinges on Quebral's definition of development being "the interaction between two social processes - development and communication" as an anchor theory and bind together the value of effective communication in establishing partnerships under CSR.

This is where communication plays a vital role, to connect people, gather resources and bring results. The private sector (Amway) becomes a responsible participant in the development process through the adoption of one public school per location near their place of operation (Makati, Manila, Cebu, Cagayan de Oro, Davao, Mandaluyong and Manila. This is where the power of Communication for Development may be applied to address the gap and limitations of such partnerships. What are the limitations of such partnerships and what are the instruments of communication used to put balance between the private companies' goals and the needs and expectations of their beneficiaries?

Describing the Socio-Political Framework, Flor (2007) mentioned that the role of communication in society is far more critical than what Libertarians or Social Responsibility advocates contend. He considers it as a major variable of social transformation, and is employed to achieve the highest social goals at the shortest amount of time. He also stated that the validation of these contemporary social science theories prove that communication has immediate and profound effects on our social and political fabric. Therefore, channeling of communication resources to worthwhile social ends at the least social cost is called for. Such is the DEVCOM perspective. In CSR

however, the social cost mentioned could be borderline between the social good and in most part the benefit of the implementer (social marketer, company, or individual sponsor.) However, the swift transformation which is a necessary end, would have been delayed or undelivered if as a society, we shall shy away from such activities. If CSR then achieves the common good, and delivers the necessary change, would society be forgiving then to accept it as a relevant discipline that could be useful and realistic as a resource for development? Considering this, can we safely say, that if the intentions to help is transparently dictated by the methods and implementation, and if the communication process between stakeholders are open to each other's scrutiny, comment, and fine-tuned based on a common ground which is development of individuals and communities, then perhaps, we can safely theorize that CSR although initiated by corporations and entities that may derive an indirect and intangible Return of Investment (ROI, like image enhancement, favorability of its public), is likewise a tool of development and is a valid ground for intermarriage between DEVCOM and CSR, with the use of communication and for the purpose of development.

In the same publication, Flor, 2007, citing both Kincaid and Schramm (1975) who borrowed certain concepts from the theory of cybernetics and came up with the convergence model which Kincaid describes as a communication process that begins with "and then..." to remind us that something has occurred before we begin to observe the process, participants come to an understanding or a mutual ground and to find improved ways of expressing himself. Such is the relationship building process between the stakeholder agreement of Amway Philippines and the Department of Education ASP Team, where the DepEd ASP Team previously meets Amway key opinion holders and

decision makers to act upon the problem which is lack of resources to sustain quality education for the majority of the population of students in public schools. Whereas Amway as a private corporation, acts upon this sharing of information through an intention of support and communicates this through the drafting of a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) which is like the guide and preamble of the mutual intention of Amway to help and the necessity of DepEd to secure support. The convergence occurs when these two major entities express the same level of understanding and agrees on the content and scope of the sponsorship package and the timeline of its delivery. Otherwise, they would have to go back to the drawing board about the projects for the partnership.

How do we use communication as a call to action for volunteers and how often should communication occur between stakeholders to deliver the expectations from both sides (beneficiary and donor)? The answer lies with how the message is framed and how efficient this is sent and distributed across stakeholders using both traditional and technology-based communications (ICTs, Social Media, email correspondences, etc.). This is where C4D becomes an ally to both the CSR practitioner and the development communicator (which may be any of the partners).

According to the Boston College Corporate Citizenship blog, CSR is an enterprise-wide responsibility and the CSR lead should be a master collaborator. As s/he goes about gathering resources and communicating the CSR plan, s/he would not only deal with the stakeholders, but also need to be closely coordinating with the Marketing Communications team. These resources are vital so that the channels of communication will be ample. Likewise, effective CSR communication is crucial in communicating the long-term value in these environmental, societal, and governance

investments of the company. Data is essential in reporting the Corporate Citizenship efforts and may be used to reinforce the business and social value of CSR projects.

In addition, the publication also shared the following steps to take for an effective Corporate Citizenship Communication Strategy:

1. Think of your plan

- a) What action do you want people to take (direction)
- b) Create a vivid image of what it looks like when you do get them to take action. (involve and mobilize)
- c) Share that image (creative communication, emotional messaging, credible reporting of statistics, etc.)

2. Craft the message

- a) Ensure that your corporate citizenship message are aligned with your overall communication strategy (Planning, creative brief, mission and vision)
- b) Remember that complexity always loses, so keep it simple and trim it down. (Short and digestible. Sensitivity to the level of communication that is applicable, and sincerity of the message)

3. Think of your audience, and the applicable language

- a) Verbal cues, vehicle to use (communication medium)

4. Reiterate the message for retention, and through various channels.

5. Report your progress. This strengthens your credibility as a communicator because sharing results and progress will create a positive impact on your audience.

6. Lastly, since this is a “collaborative effort”, it pays to share and highlight the individual or group participation in each activity. This is essential to promote the trust and confidence of both internal and external audiences.

Conceptual Framework

Communication for Development (C4D) used in CSR

Companies and members of the private sector (individually and collectively) participate in shaping society through CSR and other philanthropic acts. Projects are usually an offshoot of efforts to fill gaps where development is challenged or needed.

G. Weigel, 2004 said that the poor and the marginalized have always been at the center of development communications, but arguably as the subject of this communication rather than the originators of the communication itself. They have historically poor access to communication tools and channels.

C4D - Communication for Development as a Driver in CSR Projects

Framework 1: THE FIFTH ELEMENT - REPLICATION AND SUSTAINABILITY WITH THE HELP OF C4D AND ICTs (modified from G.Weigel, 2004)

(This adds the process of replication and sustainability through communication to G. Weigel's (2004) framework.)

He further stressed that increasing ICTs are increasing a wide range of communicators including the poor and the marginalized, to maximize their communication potential, and become significant communicators in their own

right.” Communication needs to occur in this matrix at all times, especially during the part when it becomes sustainable. In this way, the communication belongs not only to the project implementer but also the beneficiaries.

Before an event or CSR activity is set and planned, agreements that are acceptable to all stakeholders (like schedule, budget, scope and other planned related activities.)

Some agreements may be customized and targeted depending on the needs of the beneficiaries. This can only be discussed in an open dialogue, and deliberated upon with utmost transparency.

Source:

G. Weigel, "Communication for Development (C4D) as Integrated Component of the SDC ICT4D Concept and Strategy" [PowerPoint presentation], SDC, April 30 2004.

http://www.comminit.com/communicating_children/content/communication-development-c4d-tools

Conceptual Framework2: Development Model Through CSR Communications and Social Mobilization Through C4D Channels

To sum this up: CSR + C4D/ICTs + Socmob = Development

Other Related Theories - CSR Point of Views

A. Layered CSR Communication Matrix

1. Purpose Driven Communication - defining the cause and the effect (The CSR Messaging) "When it strikes near home" concept" or when CSR's impact is increased when it is deployed in a local setting (i.e. where the company headquarters is located). Another example is making CSR a

heroic act for participants (an “out-of-self” or existential experience)
“Communicating the Need” -The Social-Existentialism Theory.

2. Emotional Messaging as an effective approach to CSR and Social Mobilization. CSR has to be experiential for employees. CSR is the psychology behind people helping other people.

Steven Crowell discussed “authenticity” as an element of existentialism (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2004 & 2015).

3. Communicating the Intent to Help - Opening Channels to Stakeholders.

4. Planning and Documenting Interactions that highlight CSR numbers as an essential key indicator of social impact.

The written letters, emails, posters, social media content and other C4D Tools used in CSR Communication to drive action and mobilize resources. (See Appendix F, Appendix G, Appendix H)

B. Social Media as a Vehicle - spreading good energy through doing good. With the popularity of social media, CSR has occupied a niche in social responsibility where people interact with likes, shares, and comments. It has become a community activity that stir public action and opinion. (See Appendix I)

C. Interaction and the Infinite Possibilities - Linkages that lead to other social mobilization opportunities - Amway as part of the Direct Selling Industry, Health Supplement Industry and Association led CSR. (When companies work together to

help others and create bigger social actions. (DSAP and HADSAP Association and Amway's Participation in Industry CSR. See Appendix J)

D. Community and Development - A Symbiotic Relationship

Concept of Social Mobilization and Communication needed to mobilize stakeholders. The "need to do good" and the "need to obtain support" connects the lives of the sponsor company and the beneficiary.

E. The Amway 1K Run Case Study- Running for a Cause (and when Marketing is also CSR. Business Benefits of CSR - Because Investing in the Good is Good.

PR and Marketing as an Allied Practice – Communication Tools and Practices

In Amway's CSR Campaign, a report is sent quarterly to headquarters in Ada, Michigan, bearing the numbers to monitor annual budget spending, product donations, number of children helped, number of hours donated by the affiliate office and other significant contributions to the campaign. This is later on consolidated to the global CSR figures that the company shares for their newsroom and press. However, CSR does not always play the limelight of PR work, because Marketing the brands remain the top PR practice. Until recent times, when CSR was integrated into the marketing of the brands and was considered a brand of the company, so came the evolution of CSR as a marketing tool and a campaign for social mobilization. This gave birth to the global "Nutrilite Brand Run" which was done across South East Asia and other affiliates countries. PR and Marketing concepts are then applied in CSR.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

The researcher applied a mixed qualitative and quantitative approach which entails an ethnographical sketch of participants during the CSR activities that she implemented. This was combined with an offline FGD where statistical data was gathered to measure engagement and involvement of volunteers in the One by One Campaign for Children, and other stakeholders.

A. The research will entail conducting an offline FGD where a set of questions will be shared via an online survey (Survey Monkey) to targeted volunteers and CSR Team Leads under the Amway Philippines L.L.C. to establish the following:

1. Communication is vital and critical in CSR implementation
2. CSR results to development and improvement of the lives of beneficiaries
3. Effective CSR communication affects the overall image and favorability of the company in their public's view
4. Amway's CSR campaign (local CSR) is aligned with the company's communication plan and corporate values.

B. Impressions and views which were previously gathered during the pre-work of this research will be analyzed and presented to show the other point of view (POV) of the rest of the stakeholders namely DepEd (teachers and coordinators), Amway Management and project owners, and Team Leaders who are owners of the projects in their locality.

C. Data on impact of the program will be provided as part of the proof that CSR results to development:

- Average Number of Children helped, 2013 to 2016 data
- Amount of investments, cost of project based on (1) MOU data and (2) company budget allocation, and other relevant company investments for the CSR campaign
- Number of infrastructures built from inception in 2004 to 2016.

D. Sample communication materials will be analyzed

- Emails to employees and to partners and print material concepts
- Social media channels used and other technology-based communication channels (blogs and microsites)
- An insight about Amway's social mobilization (SOCMOB) project, the annual 1K Run to create an argument whether marketing and CSR can intermarry concepts with Development Communication practices.

Ethnography as a practice in CSR is a viable approach to effectively narrate the events within the CSR projects conducted. The best way to describe the effect of CSR is through the eyes of the stakeholders. Appreciation and involvement is also a key ingredient in effective CSR implementations under the campaign and helps sustain the interest and support of participants.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Ripple Effect in Action - The Amway One by One Campaign for Children Case Study

How can the “good” that people do for others be achieved through effective communication, and how creativity in communicating the message is important and how it helps create a beneficial working relationship in a CSR campaign?

The validity of reasons why companies implement CSR campaigns probably belongs to another forum and suffice to say that the true gist will be more on how communication becomes a catalyst in effectively building relationships the communities they touch. Development is a work not just for one person but a collective effort of many. Imagine if there are one hundred companies partnering with DepEd, then the impact can be greater.

This can be tantamount to one hundred projects for school buildings, books and educational materials, scholarship grants for deserving but poor students, computers, and many more possibilities to augment the lack of resources DepEd has, to support the schools they need to sustain annually nationwide, in the face of a shift towards K to 12 educational system.

Development Perspective - Amway Choses to Support Education-Related Advocacy

The ASEAN integration will happen whether we are ready or not. It is important that in the process of readying ourselves to face this reality, we can as a nation work together and put all our resources together to ensure that we are transitioning properly.

This is very true with all industries and sectors that will be ultimately affected by this regional integration. It is true that we cannot be left behind, and so we will at some point, calibrate and re-calibrate to compete with the rest of SEA. Globalization in fact, is another truth that we need to brace ourselves as we enter beyond 2020. The world does not wait and so we are bent to catch up on our deficiency as a nation to address this.

The hatching process maybe a slow one but the delivery of resources we need to sustain ourselves can be hastened through Public Private Partnerships such as the “Adopt-A-School Program” (ASP) under the Department of Education.

Education is very important to Filipinos. Even families belonging to the marginalized poor consider education as a passport that will take them to a better future. Likewise, the potential of the Philippines as a developing country is further enhanced with the opportunities of its people to achieve their fullest potential through accessing free quality education at least at the secondary level or the first two years of college (now equivalent to grades 11 and 12).

The shift to a new educational system took place in 2012 to address our need to advance our educational system. However, this will be long term and requires sustainable resources. Aside from a shift in curriculum and extended years of study, it will

likewise impact the lives of those affected (parents, students, educators, the government), and may need further consideration and study, increased resources provisions, including evaluating the share of the education sector national budget.

Four to five years into the actual implementation of K to 12, the need to communicate the advantages, needs, impact, and other related issues to this shift is still essential. Getting ample support through PPPs (like ASP) and CSR initiatives and streamlining these resources where they are most needed (assessment process for adoption of schools) are also important considerations. This communication process between stakeholders will be a vehicle for the delivery of the needs to support K to 12.

Amway Philippines “One by One Campaign” - Literacy Through Storytelling

Amway Global CSR campaign, One by One for Children cascades its mission and vision of "Helping People Live Better Lives" as an anchor of all affiliate-based CSR initiatives worldwide. In the Philippines, the campaign is a literacy campaign where Filipino values are integrated through storytelling (which is done by volunteer employees and distributors). In the same way, the importance of culture and employees in the volunteer process is highly stressed. Communication plays an integral part of how the "volunteer spirit" is kept alive across the organization.

In 2003, Amway Global Corporation owners Rich and Jay Van Andel decided to give back to communities where they operate through the “One by One Campaign for Children”. There are various children’s causes worldwide, and as an offshoot of this initiative, Amway Philippines partnered with the Department of Education in 2005 with education as their core thrust. Amway launched a “Literacy Through Storytelling”

Campaign and adopted their first school, Francisco Benitez Elementary School in Makati. As a result of the partnership with DepEd, a library renovation project provided a storytelling corner for their first adopted school in Makati. Amway's headquarters then was relocated to Makati City, and Francisco Benitez Elementary School was recommended as partner school due to the needs of the school and also the proximity to Amway office and their volunteers.

In 2016, the number of school library's that were renovated increased to seven school locations, and the project grew steadily, bringing values-laden stories and books to public school nationwide.

The Communication Tools Used in CSR

Person to Person Communication - How to Touch Lives with Direct Communication and Gestures

The best way perhaps to express human emotion is when a human being talks to another personally using verbal or non-verbal communication. The most important communication process is done face to face. During the initial stages, meetings between the Department of Education is set, and the intention to adopt schools are expressed by the corporate partners.

Amway started this initiative in 2003 and the partnership materialized in 2004 after the first Memorandum of Understanding was signed between Amway management and DepEd.

The Memorandum of Understanding (MOU, also known as the MOA or Memorandum of Agreement), usually span for three to five years. This is a declaration of the intention to help beneficiary schools to address a gap in their infrastructure or non-infrastructure needs.

Then the succeeding person to person communication in form of meetings and email discussions happens after the schools are selected, and the principals are convened in an initial meeting to understand their needs and how the sponsoring company is able to provide or contribute to this development project for the school.

Amway Philippines One by One Campaign for Children is a holistic campaign that involves both infrastructure and non-infrastructure support to its beneficiary schools. It builds and renovates libraries, donates storytelling books, conducts storytelling sessions and feeding programs, and raises funds to sustain other partnership projects. This is not limited to scheduled visits to conduct the literacy campaign through storytelling, but also on special projects like the annual “Brigada Eskwela Clean-up Drive” where Amway employees and distributors religiously help their beneficiary schools annually through donation of cleaning products (Amway is a distributor of organic cleaning products) and manual labor to clean classrooms in schools they support nationwide. Initially a letter is sent by DepEd to invite Amway, through the selected schools (and sometimes during kick-off events for the national office of Deped), and in turn, Amway will mobilize its resources and send out information via email, posters, and verbal announcements during company meetings and events. (See Appendix E)

Regularly, a progress report (Monthly and Quarterly Development Update) is shared via email and is also shared to employees, to show how their colleagues in various locations nationwide conduct their CSR projects on a local level. A consolidated report in powerpoint is part of the employee meetings and this boosts the morale of employees and promotes camaraderie among them.

Emotional and Psychological Benefits for Employees' Well Being

“Confidence” in Being Part of a Greater Good

The time spent to help is paid time away from the workplace. Since Amway is in retailing, employees from the operations team will be taking turns to participate, just to ensure that the business is still taken care of while the others set out to physically help the other volunteers conduct the activity. Employees who are unable to join are allowed to donate resources like food, books and also help in pre-activity preparations.

Incentivizing the Goal

In 2013, Amway CSR lead started to launch the 10 - Hour CSR Champion Journey using a passport type of card that measures the number of hours (the employees commit to complete 10 volunteer hours on the 10th year Anniversary of the Amway Global One by One Campaign. The passport became a measurement of their commitment to the campaign. On the 5th volunteer hour, the volunteer gets an Amway One by One Champion pin, then a Champion Cup on the 7th hour, and then finally a Champion Shirt on the 10th hour. One book donation was also considered “one hour” to let those who are unable to travel to complete their hours. As the years passed by, incentivizing the campaign helped drive the hours and mobilize the volunteer employees, distributors, teachers, and parents.

This also helped create a goal for everyone to show up and earn a badge that will also serve as their campaign uniform each time they participate. The badge may be just a mention and inclusion in a list of volunteers and their accomplishments which are regularly shared via group email to all employees. This will include the photos of each Amway Distribution Team or Department for the CSR activities.

The various activities are based on DepEd's annual calendar as a guide and selected activities like Brigada Eskwela (Month of May activities, in preparation for the opening of classes in June), "Linggo ng Wika" contests in Schools (August Activity), Storytelling Caravans in six locations nationwide (October to December activity) and the Annual 1K Run, a marketing event that placed the campaign as its beneficiary (fund drive and awareness campaign to build libraries and donate books).

This particularly helped mobilize different age groups, particularly the millennials who are type-casted as the "entitlement" generation. Although these were not exactly necessary to achieve the common goal, the activity of giving goals helped track the developments and gather commitment across partners and stakeholders. This project gained the target of 90% participation of all employees, and developed a sense of ownership for each Amway Distribution Center teams in all locations nationwide

Other notable CSR activities include disaster response to major calamities (e.g. Yolanda, Habagat, Ondoy, Pablo storm surge) with less than 70 employees either as project leads, facilitators, participants and manpower resources.

The 13 Hour CSR Journey used a Volunteer Card where each goal achieved was measured by a stamp placed on each hour that the volunteer employee or distributor

accomplished. This concept is patterned after the Starbucks Planner Promo, where after all stickers were completed on the promo card, a planner will be redeemed. In the case of the 13 Hour CSR Journey, the first three hours gives a volunteer a special pin bearing the campaign logo, then as s/he reaches 5 hours, a coffee mug with the campaign logo is given, then on the 10th hour, the campaign shirt with a logo, and on the 13th hour, a CSR Planner bearing photos of the CSR campaign nationwide and volunteers in action.

The Memorandum of Understanding - The CSR Agreement Guide

The first step made to reinforce the partnership the drafting of a memorandum of understanding (MOU) which contains the intention of sponsors (e.g. Amway) in sponsoring public schools near their business locations. The MOU is a legal document that stipulates the intent of a donor or partner, and the details of the project plan (scope, budget, methodology, limitation, implementation plans, time frame) and other important details such as expectations of deliverable from partners.

This document is then signed by school principals of beneficiary schools, the top company representative (usually the country manager or president), and the incumbent head or secretary of the Department of Education. To preserve the transparency between partners, the details of the project description is clearly stipulated in the MOU, and this is the “guidebook” of implementing the project throughout the partnership period which lasts for two to five years. The need to revisit the MOU details occur when additional pledges are made to donate more resources or alter project specifications.

The MOU is notarized and a seal of the Department of Education is affixed on this document. Likewise, this is the basis for the program time line and implementation details. The MOU may be changed through an addendum as needed when an adjustment in the budget or additional donations are provided by the company sponsor. This also contains specific details as to school name, location, interactions allowed between school-based volunteers, company volunteers, activities allowed and other details that may be crucial to the success of the partnership. The reason for this, is to strengthen commitment and define the expectations of both the company (Amway) and its beneficiary schools. The MOU is a written and binding commitment that gives the partnership shape and helps manage expectations from stakeholders. As soon as the MOU is drafted, agreed on and signed, the task of the Corporate Affairs Officer and the Management team is to make sure that it delivers its promise and that the children and the schools they adopted are supported based on the agreed projects.

This automatically triggers all communication between partners and is transferred and distributed faster with the advent of modern-day communications (emails, web-based communications like websites, blogs, microsites) and still sustained with the rise of mobile technology applications like social media apps, internet-based communications such as skype and FB Chat. Various communication tools like letters, agreements (Memorandum of Understanding), emails, text messaging, social media and web-based communication can drive action from stakeholders and create the necessary results to usher in development intended for beneficiaries of CSR projects. As the company's country manager, Ms. Leni Olmedo would always say, it is better for all CSR activities to be "unannounced and under the radar" to be considered a clamor to do societal good. If at

all announced, it will be at an acceptable level of exposure, and one that is just necessary to create action that is needed. The biggest challenge would be how to do targeted communication that would do this while preserving the sincerity of the campaign as an act of good will towards its beneficiaries and only ever so slightly mentioned when needed and when deemed appropriate.

Unless it would be a marketing related event like the annual run, the campaign is mainly announced to select audiences like employees, distributors, teachers, parents and DepEd ASP partners. As a Direct Selling company, Amway does not adhere to extensive advertising because it survives on the concept of “person to person” and word of mouth networking approach, even for its business format. Since its launch in the Philippines in 1997, it strived to be a quiet corporation compared to other direct selling competitors who are ever present in all media channels, and especially visible with their activities through broadcast advertising. Even so, Amway does not own a huge budget allocation for advertising its philanthropic deeds and rely mostly on its internal fuel and resources: its employees and distributors. Therefore, it relies on its communication tools and its employees to effectively implement its CSR projects.

In 2013, a MOU was drafted and approved to continue Amway’s commitment to support its existing beneficiary schools until 2017. At the time the MOU was signed, there were four schools sustained under the literacy campaign (Francisco Benitez Elementary in Makati; South City Central Elementary in Cagayan De Oro; Carreta Elementary School in Cebu; and Urdaneta I Central Elementary School in Pangasinan).

There were Amway Distribution Centers within 100 km radius of these schools. This was a consideration because communication will be difficult, and if not, impossible for a sustainable relationship.

Other Forms of Traditional Communication Used in Sustainable CSR

Corporate Messaging: The Company's Mission and Vision as a vehicle for the CSR Campaign

Corporate Social Responsibility is usually rolled out through a point person or a "CSR Lead" who may be a part or a representative of the management team. The reason for this is because CSR can only thrive if supported with the company's mission and vision, and its management. Approvals for projects may be difficult if a CSR project is not aligned with what the company wants to accomplish as a responsible corporate citizen.

In the case of Amway, the global corporation's mission and vision is to "Help People Live Better Lives." Next to this, Amway, a family owned, US based corporation claims to offer entrepreneurship opportunities to over 3 million distributors, almost 20,000 employees globally, position themselves as a world leader in the direct selling industry who operates in over 100 countries worldwide, with over USD 8.8 billion in sales and revenue (https://www.amwayglobal.com/en_us/about.html.) In its earlier years, the Amway One by One Campaign was anchored on children's causes (then known as "One by One Campaign for Children"). In 2013, during its 10th year anniversary, Amway Global headquarters in Michigan reported helping over 10 million children worldwide through

children's causes that range from addressing developmental problems like lack of proper nutrition, cancer in children, or education, among others.

In 2016, a new direction took place, while allowing the local affiliates local campaign to thrive based on the needs of local communities, a new thrust to focus on the fight against malnutrition (to address SDG 2) was globally spearheaded, side by side its position in the Health and Nutrition Industry.

The messaging of fighting malnutrition as a call to action was launched in several affiliates and countries where malnutrition was rampant (Africa, Southeast Asia, etc.) and gathering up resources from its Nutrilite Brand "Power of 5" to make sure children who are in the initial stages of their growth (age 1 to 5) will be provided with the proper nutrition necessary for them to survive into their growing years.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, where there are only around an estimated 75 employees (2016 data), the literacy project with DepEd is in place until School Year 2018; and by 2017, Amway Philippines have provided help to some 10,000 children in the form of school supplies donation, books, library renovation projects, and other sponsorship projects for education related initiatives under ASP.

The question is how can a small volunteer base support and sustain a nationwide campaign in six locations with 75 employees (90% of whom are actively engaged in CSR) and minimal financial resources? Communication is the key.

The partnership was forged using a MOU template which designates the responsibilities of Amway and DepEd. Aside from these, communication through traditional means (phone, fax, posters are also widely used) and very recently, in 2011,

the use of email communication had increased the ability of the program director/officer to cascade the information to all stakeholders.

Communication is used not only as a tool to disseminate information but also as a tool to mobilize resources (manpower and funding) for the CSR campaign.

Stages of the Communication Process and Tools Used

A. Concept to Agreement

1. MOU - Memorandum of Agreement

Sets parameters of the partnership and includes intent to adopt, program method (literacy campaign, in the case of Amway), budget, resources and timelines. (Refer to Appendix 1)

2. Deed of Donation - specifies the donation details like if it falls under infrastructure or non-infrastructure, cost of donation, particulars (timeline) and agreeing parties (Amway and adopted school. (See Appendix 2)

B. Implementation Stage : Communication Tools for Sustainability

1. Partnership Letters - This may come in written format or sent through machines like facsimile, or actual mailed letters from government. (see Appendix 3)

2. Emails - sent from the program facilitator to partners (e.g. letters to staff seeking support and highlighting activity schedule which are sent periodically to remind them of their roles in the projects.

3. Other examples are emails from teachers and principals seeking support from Amway for projects like Brigada Eskwela, donation drives for disaster relief of schools affected by calamities (e.g. Yolanda aftermath. See Appendix 4)

4. Posters and Flyers - 1K Run Flyers sent to target supporters of the fundraising campaign to build libraries for public schools nationwide. This doubles as a product promotion marketing event with a chosen beneficiary. (See Appendix)

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

An FGD with 10 respondents was conducted using an online survey on October 7, 2017.

Participants included employees (management and staff), teachers, and distributors.

- 80 percent of respondents believed that the program was carried out successfully.
- 30 percent of respondents said that social media is one of the commonly used methods of communicating. Meanwhile, 20 percent said emails are more common, while 50 percent said that mixed methods are used throughout the implementations.
- The CSR lead scored high in communicating ahead of the implementation. This is crucial to the success of each project.
- 80 percent of the respondents are active volunteers and participants.
- Respondents scores are high when it comes to favorability of the campaign, saying it is aligned with the company message and given the chance, they will participate again in the activities.

(See Appendix K)

Summary

Social Mobilization and CSR Communication in Action: The Nutrilite Run Project (also known as Amway 1K Run) and how 16,000 runners built a library in 2011.

The Key Messaging Tool: Running for Health and a Cause

Social mobilization is an important CSR practice that helps accomplish the herculean task of bringing a social development goal into fruition. In 2011, Amway Philippines, while striving to grow its distributor base, came up with a marathon run called “Amway 1K Run”. The objective was to raise awareness about the company through a benefit race that will also build a library in Davao, where an Amway Distribution Center was located.

Runners were distributors and non-distributors who paid minimal fees for the race shirt and bib (P300 per runner). Proceeds of P10 was then funneled into the One by One Campaign for Children literacy campaign. Throughout the marketing campaign of the event, the message on how the company aims to raise funds for its beneficiaries was highlighted on the flyers.

Likewise, runners were given the option for free registration to the Amway Business (which was worth Php 1,000) during the time of implementation (thus coining “1K Run as a concept”.) The key message was even more meaningful when teachers from all five current beneficiary schools, and one recently adopted school in 2012 (Lacson Elementary School in Calinan Davao) joined this run, alongside Amway employees, distributors and run enthusiasts.

The program was announced in radio stations, flyers and posters were published in major and local newspapers, posted or distributed in areas that were hubs of foot traffic like malls, nearby transport stations and in social media assets of Amway.

Charity runs were trending activities even for regular marketing promotions of other companies. A competitor, Avon Philippines also launched a similar awareness campaign called the annual “Kiss Goodbye to Breast Cancer” in 2002, where proceeds were used to support women’s causes, particularly breast cancer awareness.

See (<http://www.pinoyfitness.com/2011/07/avon%E2%80%99s-race-to-125000-kisses-run-october-2-2011/comment-page-3/>).

In December 4, 2016, Herbalife, another Nutrition and Direct Selling company (Philippines office) conducted their 5K Fun Run which celebrates their 22nd anniversary.

(Source:<https://runadoboking.wordpress.com/2016/12/08/herbalife-philippines-celebrates-22nd-anniversary-with-fun-run-nutrition-day/>)

Similar patterns on the messaging is consistent with these companies CSR campaigns (Amway as a nutrition advocate through its Nutrilite Brand, Avon as a company for women, and Herbalife as a nutrition company) illustrates how companies create the events and eventually achieve their CSR objectives alongside their business activities.

Again, the researcher stresses that this study is not about the morality of such marketing-based CSR but how the results were delivered through effective CSR

communication. Channels such as print, electronic, and social media were extensively and simultaneously utilized to reach their target audience - the public. (see Appendix I)

Looking at how CSR operates in these three examples, we can infer that companies do align their key messages, and use these to support relevant causes and social responsibility projects.

Going back to Amway's 1K Run, the library renovation project for a school located in the outskirts of Davao City for some 300 students, was finally started in June 2013, a year after the 1K Run was launched. In the span of two years after the first library project funded by the run was built, two other schools were adopted and libraries were renovated annually in 2014, 2015 respectively. (See Appendix c for photos of beneficiary schools and their library projects that were completed using the run proceeds.)

CSR and Social Existentialism:

Aside from traditional partnerships with government, Amway also partnered with Museo Pambata, a non-profit organization which runs the children's museum in the heart of Manila. Museo Pambata is a staunch collaborator in Amway's literacy campaign and helped them communicate the message of instilling values, through a storytelling training they have made for all volunteers (Amway staff, Amway Distributors/ABO (Amway Business Owners), teachers and community volunteers.

Through this training, all the participants were given an intensive program where they immerse in storytelling methods (conventional and creative storytelling techniques like shadow playing, puppeteering, among others. Museo also became a channel for Amway to reach the street children of Manila, in cooperation with LGU and community

organizers. Children of a diverse origin, who were usually sleeping in the streets were gathered in pocket storytelling sessions that double as feeding programs and are conducted by the Amway employees outside of their work hours. Books and clothing are donated and gathered as a result of posters and campaign letters routed organization-wide and to Amway Distributor Centers to seek social support and stir concern from volunteers for the campaign.

Andreasen (2006)

Stakeholders Analysis - Amway and DepEd, Building Sustainable Relationships Through Effective Communication

- Meeting Expectations - Estimated 1Million Annually for Corporate Social Responsibility (Creating Impact with a Limited Budget). MOU budget is PHP 2.5M spread across the implementing years from SY 2013 to 2018.
- Sharing Resources to Bridge Gaps - Supporting School Related

Activities:

- Brigada Eskwela - Manpower and Product Donation
- Linggo Ng Wika Contests - Competition Based support for students based on their talents (prizes of contests, food for participants and volunteers)
- Calamity Related Support - Drawing resources from employees, distributors, regional headquarters, and global office (e.g. Yolanda/Haiyan Tacloban Drive)

- The Communication Channels using the C4D Matrix
- The Impact - 7 Library Renovations in 7 years and Other Stories
of Uplifting the Lives of Others: The 5th Element

C4D and Replicating Results

Since its launch in 2003, Amway One by One has helped countless communities globally. Through its key messaging of “Helping People Live Better Lives”, a culture of social giving is encapsulated in the company’s mission and vision, and has been an anchor or social awareness for its employees and distributors worldwide. (see global numbers in 2016).

In the Philippines, through its partnership with DepEd, it has vowed to build and renovate at least one school in any location where the Amway business operates.

2004 saw the donation of a Storytelling Corner for Francisco Benitez School in Makati where the Amway Headquarters was located.

Between 2005 and 2016, six other schools benefited from the renovation projects in Cebu (Carreta Elementary School), Cagayan de Oro (South City Central Elementary School), Urdaneta Pangasinan (Urdaneta I Central Elementary School, Highway Hills Integrated School in Mandaluyong, and recently in 2016, in the heart of Manila (Rafael Palma Elementary School).

In 2011 when Amway Marketing team, in collaboration with the Nutrilite Brand, created Amway 1K Run where the CSR Brand, One by One Campaign for Children will be a beneficiary of part of the proceeds. The 2011 run managed to gather over 16,000

runners (employees, distributors and their families, friends, and the public). The run fee which covers a singlet shirt, and some free products and access to the booths costed Php 595. The amount partially covered costs of the run, and Php 10 pesos per runner went to the campaign. Aside from providing an exhilarating experience to its patrons and distributors, the run also created an opportunity for the company to help renovate at least one library and donate storytelling books. This practice became an annually implemented Marketing and CSR project that sustained the partnership thrust between DepEd and Amway, and its stakeholder (employees, distributors, teachers, and LGUs).

Each Amway provincial location conducted their own 1K Run (Cagayan De Oro, Davao, Cebu and Baguio) during the initial run launch. In succeeding years, the three main areas retained this as an annual marketing activity. The run also allowed non-Amway distributors who participated in the run to sign-up for an Amway business ownership without cost (membership fees then costed Php 2,000, then was recently lowered to Php 1,000 during the launch of 1K Run, which signified the cost of the Amway Kit as well.) and increasing the chance of the community to entrepreneurship opportunities with the company. The membership entitled the product users and the business owners to buy the products at distributors price which is lower than the retail value. In direct selling, it is important to add value to its members through a business plan that allows them to grow based on their effort index. This also allows them to get travel incentives (local and international) based on their performance. For consumers, the benefit would include access to world class core products that were backed by research and science (Nutralite brand, Artistry Brands, and Home Care Brands). The method of which is person to person (direct selling), and relies mostly on testimonies of users on the

quality of the products they use. 1K Run was designed for the purpose of letting people know about the company and also to inscribe the CSR component of what the company does for the community. This perspective makes the activity a “cross-breed” between just “marketing” and into a social awareness and mobilization project for the schools that Amway supports. The proceeds donated to schools are on top of the annual one million pesos annual budget for the schools adopted under DepEd.

Runners included the teachers and principals of the schools (beneficiaries) which helps them to address their needs for recreation and as a symbol of support for the campaign (teachers can run for free and get the same benefits as the other runners.)

A booth for all brands were put up in the run location (usually done in the Mall of Asia grounds) so that the runners will fully experience Amway as a company. The booth for the CSR campaign, One by One Campaign becomes a station for the beneficiaries who ran and the distributors who wanted to interact with them (social interaction, person to person communication) and solidifies the relationship of both the sponsors (Amway), partners (DepEd), and other stakeholders (Amway employees, distributors.) The CSR Booth also became a venue for fund raising, where runners may opt to buy a book for donation to the schools. Actual books were sold on site, but were later turned in to the schools who participated. Funds from such activities were used to buy the schools materials they need (electric fans, books, paint for facilities, and others.) (see Appendix 10 for run photos)

CSR benefits most from social marketing practices, and makes it a chance for companies to creatively communicate the “good” in their intentions.

Conclusion

C4D applied in CSR Leads to Development

Communication plays a pivotal role in human interaction. Development meanwhile is the desired effect of collective human actions that result from an effective communication process. In CSR, these two concepts are intermarried and are essential to achieve the final objective which is to “communicate the good” and “bring positive change” in the lives of individuals and communities where Corporate Social Responsibility projects are expected to help or alleviate the situation, or address the developmental need or gap, whether short term or long term, or if it applies to incremental or massive change. In the hatching process as described in the development process must not be forced, but sustainable.

We are all Connected

Transcend beyond yourself and see the world through the eyes of many. Cross the line between knowledge into a world of authentic understanding. Be one with the collective whole and be the spiritual awakening this world needs. For whatever you do, reflects back to you. You are what you share to this world. We are connected, we are the change that we want to be. Your story is an imprint in the hearts of the people you touch.

When helping others becomes a collective vision, then and only then can the world experience the true essence of humanity. Development can happen in places where an awakening of such collective commitments exists.

CSR uses communication extensively throughout the implementation process. As a result, development is ushered in (see Yellow Boat of Hope project under DepEd's ASP) and in so many ways, companies may also benefit in terms of promoting employee well-being, as employees trust their company more as a place of holistic development and more than just a place for work. (see attached interview responses). They identify themselves as capable of heroic deeds (social existentialism) and through ample and adequate messaging, they are stirred to action towards societal good. As a collective group, having a collective vision, the stakeholders are given a clear grasp of their huge role in making things happen for those who need it most through effective messaging tools.

CSR and Communication for Development are an allied Discipline

Communicating the good is a good practice whether you are an individual or a corporation, and CSR is an offshoot of this social marketing concept. We need more of these to make things better for underdeveloped communities and to remove the barriers of development. And the faster we become part of such movements, whether as an individual or a group, the more areas we can cover. In a developing country scenario such as the Philippines setting, the ills of corruption and unequal distribution of wealth are some of the impediments for the poor to have access to basic human necessities and rights. If

this barrier is removed, then we can be assured that we can at some point, lessen the lack of opportunities, and assistance for those who actually need it.

While we wait on our government to mature in terms of resources and prioritization, we can only do so much as to combine external resources from both the government, the public and the private sectors, not as a stop gap solution but as an aid to provide “quick access” to the poor. As Quebral said, development should be swift to address the development problems society faces.

Communication for Development (C4D) hastens the process of communication between stakeholders. The augmented C4D Matrix (see page 15 for the conceptual framework) includes how to make the projects sustainable using the various forms of communication and technology used in transferring the knowledge and concept of the campaign.

Recommendations

C4D Tools, at the heart of this matrix would include emails and other computer aided communication used. These may also include the social media platforms like social media applications (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and microsites, blogs, online newsrooms.)

Traditional communication utilized like letters, agreements, implementing memorandums, invitations to partners and volunteers, posters are also extensively used, and the PDF formats of which are also redistributed through emails and posted on social media and website resources.

A striking balance should be used to achieve the goals and objectives of the CSR Campaign. In the case of Amway, email was extensively used across stakeholders to bridge the distance between the Makati headquarters where the project lead was based, and the various teams in the different Amway Distribution Center locations nationwide. Every project is guided by an implementing memo which is the basis of all implementations for all adopted schools (see Appendix F) and the same budget is implemented across (except for the transportation necessary to reach the areas where schools are located, since provincial travel is required, including airfare for management and staff involved in the CSR activities.)

The 5 Pillars of C4D Communications (represented by the circles on page 39, Conceptual Framework derived from G. Weigel, 2004)

1st Pillar/Element: Building Capacity - Includes the practice of gathering resources to support and sustain the projects under the campaign. Communication includes meeting with Headquarters and Regional Counterparts to seek approval of annual budget (management and CSR Lead role) and communicating to DepEd how this annual budget will be used to achieve the targeted improvement in the adopted schools. This also includes communication to team leaders in different locations and their respective adopted schools (e.g. Amway Cebu Distribution Center takes care of its local school, Carreta Elementary).

2nd Pillar/Element: Networking and Dialogue - Communication is opened to all stakeholders from the planning to implementation. Certain levels of approvals are achieved (e.g. management approves the school adopted through a presentation of the

planned adoption, then DepEd agrees to the planned improvement through an exchange of emails and project discussions via email, phone, or in person). Meanwhile, teams gather support from local distributors of Amway in their communities to monitor and implement the project.

3rd Pillar/Element: Amplification and Distribution - C4D accomplishes this as computer-based communications like emails, web posts, social media and others make it easier to disseminate the message and announcements.

4th Pillar/Element: Capturing and Recording the Events and Progress: A monthly progress report for each beneficiary school is reported during the employee general assembly. This presentation is also shared with the regional office and global headquarters. The report includes data on the project impact (number of children helped, amount of donation in terms of cash and kind, number of volunteer hours spent for the campaign, and highlights on citations for the local teams from DepEd Regional Office or their adopted school).

5th Pillar/Element: Sustainability (Securing Financial Resources, Management Approval and Support, and Revitalizing the Partnership)

A. Company Initiated - a basic fund is allocated annually and is managed by the management team, through a coordinator or project manager. The project manager meanwhile works on an annual project plan (AOP - Annual Operating Plan) as part of the fulfillment of Key Performance Indicators (e.g., impact result like number of schools helped, number of employees engaged in the projects, or number of distributor leaders involved). A report is usually presented (in MS

Powerpoint, C4D Tool) to show the plan, then a detailed budget is drawn to sustain this).

B. Employee Initiated - when key leaders in various location receive communication via email from a project coordinator, the implementing memo serves as the blue print for a nationwide roll-out of the project. The email communication is sent first to the team leaders prior to a general communication (call to action) to employees and distributors who want to participate. This is commonly done through posters, emotional messaging (key message is why there is a need to help and who will benefit).

In all Amway Philippines provincial location, the employees are often encouraged to help their own beneficiary school (e.g. Davao City helps a small elementary school in Calinan, Davao City, Lacson Elementary School which is an hour and a half away from the Amway Distribution Center in Davao City. “We take care of our own” and this becomes a rally for social involvement. Each team belongs to a school outreach project and there is ownership of the project at local level. The stories documented are then shared via email to all employees to show positive communication across the organization. This establishes the fact that corporate citizenship is not just a PR campaign but helps the well-being of people and society. Employees look forward to each activity with a zeal of passion because of the “non-material” benefits like work-life balance, social interaction, and teamwork.

Government as an indirect beneficiary of these projects also extend their message of thanks through a regular stakeholders’ meeting “Appreciation Meeting” held at least

twice or thrice a year at the Department of Education, Main Office in Ortigas, Pasig where partners are gathered and given citations for their contribution. At local level, schools also provide certificates of appreciation to their partner companies like Amway. This simple written certificate seals the partnership and gives the company a reason to continue its support.

C. Partner Initiated

1. DepEd Brigada Eskwela and the call to help provide conducive classrooms before each school year. Traditionally, a “Brigada Eskwela Cleanup Drive” is annually set in the month of May to get the classrooms prepped for incoming students. This is a call to action for existing partners to support not only the adopted schools but also those areas who need support. This is exemplified during the Tacloban Brigada Eskwela where Amway employees flew to Tacloban to help clean classrooms, donate cleaning materials, and books for the victims of Yolanda. Usually, an email is sent by the DepEd main office to all ASP Partners (like Amway) and a confirmation would lead for a pocket activity planning where a budget may be drawn from the annual CSR budget as part of an outreach.

2. Museo Pambata Outreach: Museo Pambata is an independent non-government organization and is Amway’s partner in conducting storytelling trainings for its volunteers nationwide. Each time a school is adopted, Museo Pambata trainers conduct group trainings for employees, school teachers and volunteer parents and distributors of Amway. In recent developments, an outreach program to help the children of Luneta was launched (about 25 to 30 children were invited for each outreach) where

children were given food and encouraged participate in the storytelling sessions and art activities. Kids were invited through their local LGUs and through non-formal invitations (person to person). Targeted audience were ages 3 to 12 years old, most of whom are either homeless or living in depressed areas. Communication used to invite volunteers are emails, person to person (face to face), and through social media (facebook).

3. Analysis of communication used for CSR (See Page 93 to 105 for email samples and attachments used)

<u>Type of Communication</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Purpose</u>	<u>Tone of message</u>	<u>Audience</u>
Email to Employees	Once a week, or after each project is successfully rolled out	Announcements of activities, project progress etc.	Conversational, instructional, informative, inspirational, uses call to action, includes success stories	employees and management team of Amway (General Manager and Country Manager, Executives)
Emails to Project Team Leads	Before every project launch, and after for validation	To brief on mechanics of programs, and update on project roll out dates and implementation	conversational, instructional, informative, inspirational, uses call to action	selected team leaders nationwide
Email to Partners/DepEd	During MOU drafting and signing. Then as needed. During initial intent to adopt a school,	To update on project plans, dates, budgetary concerns and other related support activities.	Formal, specific details are mentioned, agreements based, professional tone.	DepEd and Management of Amway

Posters	on a per activity basis	announcement of activities, pre-event preparations	PR/marketing type, emotional messaging, visual and uses action photos or call to action	Amway Distributors volunteers
Website	annual program updates, including regional and global updates.	To inform general public on activities of the local campaign, One by One Campaign for Children	Professional, Statistics driven, Facts of the campaign and objectives are stressed.	General Public, Distributors of Amway and other internal and external partners
Microsite	per project postings	To inform general public on activities of the local campaign, One by One Campaign for Children	campaign focussed activities and resources	General Public, Distributors of Amway and other internal and external partners
Blogs	per event postings	To inform general public on activities of the local campaign, One by One Campaign for Children	storytelling mode, general appeal for public consumption, includes success stories and extraordinary efforts of volunteers.	General Public, Distributors of Amway and other internal and external partners
Facebook	per event postings	To inform general public on activities of the local campaign, One by One Campaign for Children	on a per event or per need basis. To increase virality of the campaign and public participation (e.g. Nutrilite Health Run, a marketing campaign that	General Public, Distributors of Amway and other internal and external partners

			benefits the CSR projects.)	
Reports	During monthly employee meetings or as needed	To personally update employees about significant activities, statistics and other facts about the campaign.	conversational, uses powerpoint presentations, slideshows, videos, or internet based links for global resources on child causes (worldview, devcom approach)	Employees, management and sometimes top distributors (during major events)

Bibliography:

Bandalaria, M. (2014). Social Marketing and Social Mobilization for Development. Dev 208 Module. University of the Philippines Open University.

McKee, N. (2004). Social Mobilization and Social Marketing in Developing Communities: Lessons for Communicators.

Velasco et. al. (1999). Social Marketing and Social Mobilization for Development

Flor, A.G. (2007). Development Communication Praxis. Chapter 10, Communication, Culture, and the Collective Mind, 99-109.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276929356_Development_Communication_Praxis

Quebral, N. (2006). Development Communication in a Borderless World. <https://ojs.mau.se/index.php/glocaltimes/article/view/52/48>

Smith, K. (2014). Corporate Citizenship 2014, Five Areas for Continued Action. Boston College for Corporate Citizenship.

<https://ccc.bc.edu/content/ccc/blog-home/2014/01/blog-2014-01-corporate-citizenship-2014-five-areas-for-continued-action.html>

Morsing, M. & Scultz, M. (2006). Corporate Social Responsibility Communication: Stakeholder information, response and involvement strategies. Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1467-8608.2006.00460.x>

Andreasen, A.R. (2006). Social Marketing in the 21st Century. Roles for Community, 131-132.

Weigel, G. (2004) "Communication for Development (C4D) as Integrated Component of the SDC ICT4D Concept and Strategy" [PowerPoint presentation], SDC, April 30 2004.

Chandler, D. (2015). Corporate Social Responsibility, A Strategic Perspective. Strategic CSR as a Value Creation, 123-132.

Kotler, P. & Lee, N. (2005). Corporate Social Responsibility, Doing the Most Good for Your Company and Your Cause. "Corporate Philanthropy: Making a Direct Contribution to a Cause," 145-206

The Department of Education, Adopt A School Program

<http://doleintlcsr.com/philippines-adopt-a-school-program-2/>

Philippine Statistics Agency website, Data on Education and Literacy
https://www.psa.gov.ph/sites/default/files/2015%20PIF%20Final_%20as%20of%20022916.pdf

The Report, The Philippines 2015, Oxford Business Group and Punongbayan and Araullo
<https://oxfordbusinessgroup.com/philippines-2015>

Amway Website. Corporate Social Responsibility, Improving Global Communities.
<https://www.amwayglobal.com/corporate-social-responsibility/>

Mirvis, P. et al. (2008). "Building Reputation Here, There and Everywhere; Worldwide Views on local impact of Corporate Social Responsibility"

Appendix A

Partnerships and Literacy Campaign Photos in Adopted Schools

(Below a sample of one of the appreciation certificates from DepEd to Amway Philippines, issued by F. Benitez. Elementary School.)

APPENDIX B

Library Infrastructure and Beneficiary Schools

Schools Supported by the Campaign: Photo Collage

This was taken in Highway Hills Integrated School, Mandaluyong, a storytelling session by management, employees, distributors, teachers and parents. 30 children, 20 volunteers.

Top of picture shows Finance Manager and Warehouse Operations Supervisor conducting the storytelling session for grade one students. Below picture shows an Amway Diamond Distributor in an informal storytelling session.

Amway top distributor leads volunteers in her area in Mandaluyong, Highway Hills Integrated Elementary School. This was the first adopted school under K to 12 which included a package for Kasaysayan ng Pilipinas books for their library.

APPENDIX C

Yolanda Relief Drive

A. Tacloban in ruins. Photo taken three months after the onslaught of Yolanda.

APPENDIX D

Rizal Elementary School and the Yolanda Brigada Eskwela Outreach in Tacloban, May 2013

Picture shows Amway Country Manager, Leni Olmedo during the donation of cleaning products for a Yolanda affected school in Tacloban City.

APPENDIX E

BRIGADA ESKWELA IN DAVAO CITY IN PARTNERSHIP WITH DEPED'S

ADOPT A SCHOOL PROGRAM

Amway employees, LGUs, Teachers and parents clean a beneficiary school in Calinan, Davao.

APPENDIX F

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS FOR CSR TIE UPS WITH PR AND MARKETING. AND OTHER INTERNAL / EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION TOOLS.

Posters / 1K Run Photos

1K Run Poster (above picture) with proceeds going to Amway One by One Campaign. Below picture shows management, employees and distributors run for a cause.

Senior Management Team leading the nationwide Fun Run where proceeds go to the One by One Campaign for Children.

APPENDIX G

Letters and Agreements used in the One by One Campaign

The MOU Agreement

See attached proposed MOU (not for publication due to content privacy).

APPENDIX H

The Implementing Memo Example

Implementing Memo

2016 CSR 13 Hour Awards: Nationwide Activity

December Global Volunteer Month

I. Objectives:

- a. Create awareness of the new campaign and extend the CSR Awards to encourage ABO engagement through a Gen Y/ U35 approach "celebrating our victories".
- b. Celebrate the Global 13th year of One by One Campaign under the "Be the Change in Your Community" Battle-Cry.
- c. Final culminating event with a fund raising event based on a "peso value equivalent per product donation"

II. Theme: "A Toast for Good Deeds: One by One Global World Volunteer Day", Awards Night Fund Drive.

Concept: Platform: Similar to AMCHAM Charity Ball

Venue: Amway ADC Makati

V. Mechanics:

Certificate Awards are available for top ten awardees, first 10 finishers of 13 volunteer hours in ADCs starting November 15 to December 1. *With a symbolic prize for top ten finisher awardees. **Refer to qualifications below

****Qualifications:**

1. Must be the first ten finishers in 5 ADC locations including Amway Head office
2. Must be a bonafide Amway Philippines ABO, or employee
3. With a total of 13 cumulative volunteer hours
4. Have participated in two (2) volunteer events (storytelling, book donation or a combination of both)
5. Is a registered volunteer in any of the following ADC or Amway affiliate office:

- a. ADC Makati
- b. ADC Mandaluyong
- c. ADC CDO
- d. ADC Davao
- e. ADC Cebu
- d. Amway Head Office

***Additional CSR/Marketing Promo: Buy Php 10,000 worth of Amway Products on November Freedom Friday and get 1 free pass to the event. Php 50 goes to the campaign.

III. Budget:

Php 60,000 for symbolic artisan clocks (handmade drawing 60 pcs @Php 1,000)
 Php 50,000 for ADC based kick off ceremony on December 4 (healthy cocktails)
 Wine. Makati ADC Kickoff c/o Makati Shangri-la wines (complimentary, on hand).
 Php 100,000 worth of virtual e-GCs (TBC, projected only)
 (max target 500 x Php 300 Volunteers, between Php 100,000 to 150,000)
Total Budget: Php 210,000 (budgeted, 2016)

IV. Communication Tools: announcement spiel

We are Connected, and Today is the TIME to Be The Change In Our Communities.

Our lives are like thread sewn to form a dynamic network; each human life, significantly stitched to one other. What does this mean? Human beings are created to make a difference in the lives of people they touch, and once a connection is made, the possibilities to help others are endless.

We can never go wrong when we let kindness inside our hearts. This is what the world needs: hearts sewn together with an invisible thread that creates an unbreakable force that removes barriers, uplifts human conditions, and makes every interaction matter. Hours dedicated to help others, is time well spent. We then bring you the challenge to be at the core of this phenomenal transformation of people and communities.

"Do you have the TIME to make a difference in the lives of others? "

This December, we celebrate the spirit of volunteerism and raise the bar for community building as we award our 13 hour One by One Campaign Volunteers with Php 300 worth of Amway e-GC which they may use to buy products at any ADC nationwide.

Plus a ***surprise token for the first 50 finishers of the 13 hour journey (Top 10 in all 5 volunteer locations like ADC Mandaluyong, ADC Makati, ADC Shaw. To know more, register as a volunteer in any of our ongoing Campaign activities nationwide.**

***On a while supplies last basis**

***Will be arranged for shipping to other provincial based ADC and awarded in any CSR or Freedom Friday event.**

Approvals:

PAV

DBR

LPO

A. Email Communication Sample - How to Evoke Emotional Messaging to Mobilize Volunteers Using Development Communication Concepts

Email 1. Announcement to Mobilize Employees to Participate

- Conversational
- Time Bound (calendared)
- Positive Messaging (encourages ownership, highlights roles)
- Use of ICTs like computers to send and receive emails, and access resources like microsities and online galleries. The need for intranet and internet access makes this easy for the communicator and the recipients.
- Inclusive - sent to all staff and management, posters are usually displayed at point of contact for volunteers (Amway Distribution Center) and person to person invitation and coordination is done by local teams to inform the coordinators of the respective school.
- Project Status is updated and up-to date

Sample Email

From: Michelle Ochoa

Sent: Saturday, March 05, 2016 11:30 AM

To: PHL.All.Staff <PHL.All.Staff@amway.com>

Subject: One by One Campaign Updates and Relaunch of Online Auction Site

Dear **CSR Champions**,

It is almost vacation time for our beneficiary students and we know that we are soon nearing our annual “Brigada Eskwela” cleanup drive. Let us do a warm up activity through gathering support for them, as we go toward school year 2016 to 2017. Good news that this week, we will be purchasing one projector for our planned e-library for Palma Elementary from proceeds of our [auction last November \(Team ADC Mandaluyong & Team ADC Makati, under Hany Magpantay and Mike Vallente\)](#). Construction will be underway and we are excited to share that we will soon have another place to visit for our campaign activities this June.

Rafael Palma Elementary School

City of Manila

Team HO

Team leader: Aileen Gragera

Assistant Team Leader: Angelique Lara Corbilla
Library Project Coordinators: Cody Tambis, Bojie De Leon, Michelle Ochoa
Library Project Target Ground Breaking: March, 4th week
Library Turnover: May 2016 (During Brigada Eskwela)
Funded in part by Nutrilite NHR Manila, CDO, and Davao proceeds

We thank all of you for your support and help and invite you again to view the remaining artworks that are open for sponsorship. You may still complete your 12th hour until March 31 and join our 2nd batch of awardees in May 2016! Then in April, we thread our next Volunteer Champions step under the “13 Hours Journey.”

You may visit our site at <http://www.obolikhangkamay.xyz/> or click this to donate and help support our beneficiaries nationwide <http://www.obolikhangkamay.xyz/auction-form/> with password [hope](#).

-
To view remaining artworks, click here <http://www.obolikhangkamay.xyz/category/artworks/>
[Click here](#) for our [Hall of Champions for Good](#).

Warm regards,

Michelle Punongbayan- Ochoa

**Corporate Affairs and Executive Officer | Office of the Country
Manager**

Feliza Bldg. G/F 108 Rufino St., corner Dela Rosa Legaspi Village, Makati
City

T: +632-8148181 ext 1802 | F: +632-8927909(DL/telefax)

Michelle.ochoa@amway.com +639178898181

This email is intended only for the named person or entity to which it is addressed and may contain valuable business information that is privileged, confidential and/or otherwise protected from disclosure. Dissemination, distribution or copying of this email or the information herein by anyone other than the intended recipient, or an employee, or agent responsible for delivering the message to the intended recipient, is strictly prohibited. All contents are the copyright property of the sender. If you are not the intended recipient, you are nevertheless bound to respect the sender’s worldwide legal rights. We require that unintended recipients

delete the email and destroy all electronic copies in their system, retaining no copies in any media.

Email 2 : Announcement for the Storytelling Training for Volunteers and Auction Event

- Conversational
- Defined roles of participants
- Defined time frame
- Highlight participation and leadership roles
- Use of #SDG4 and microsite link
- Transparency in donation proceeds
- Traditional poster printout of attachment was used

From: Michelle Ochoa

Sent: Tuesday, November 10, 2015 11:01 AM

To: PHL.All.Staff <PHL.All.Staff@amway.com>

Subject: Amway One by One Anniversary activities and updates

Dear **CSR Champions**,

Sharing with you an updated list of attendees for the **Certificate Storytelling Training** on November 13, 2015 with Museo Pambata. On this list are teachers and parent volunteers from our 3 Manila based schools namely F. Benitez, Highway Hills Integrated, and Rafael Palma Elementary School (a library project that will be funded in part with proceeds from the upcoming Nutrilite Run in 2016. **Thanks Nutrilite!**).

Also further down, below this email is an updated list of those who already placed their pledge/support for the children's artworks, prior to the auction night on November 27. **Thank you Team ADC Makati** and our Auction Curator /Leader, Hany Magpantay for her efforts! More artworks are available online when you visit www.obolikhankamay.xyz and the password for the auction form is **hope**. This November, Thursday is volunteer day so we encourage you to wear our One by One 12 Hours shirt (blue) to celebrate the task before us to help children live better lives. **Help a child fulfill his/her dream, support a community in raising the next**

generation of leaders, and ensure that our nation will rise towards its full potential! Happy Volunteering! #SDG4

LIST OF ATTENDEES FOR NOVEMBER 13 ONE BY ONE CAMPAIGN FOR CHILDREN

B. BENITEZ ELEMENTARY SCHOOL – under the Team ADC Makati : Hany Magpantay (Team Leader)/Grace Mogol (Asst. Leader)

1. Mrs. Maricris S. Oga-Oga
2. Mr. Ruthchiel H. Parcon
3. Ms. Dona Liza V. Dela Cruz
4. Ms. Analyn G. Ordonio
5. Ms. Joan A. Rodriguez
6. Ms. Joy P. Ventura
7. Mrs. Norma G. Lup-Ac
8. Mrs. Joyce C. Arisgado
9. Mrs. Ida J. Rafols
10. Mr. Ricky Tabudlong
11. Mrs. Maria Luisa Sibayan
12. Mrs. Vilma V. Bermillo
13. Mrs. Josephine Andeza
14. Mrs. Mildred Bugarin
15. Mrs. Ma. Melissa N. Deposa
16. Mrs. Josephine R. Libradilla
17. Mrs. Maria Theresa V. Aguilar
18. Mrs. Marissa Quintero

HIGHWAY HILLS INTEGRATED SCHOOL (under Team ADC Mandaluyong – Mike Vallente (Team Lead)/Jenn Diaz (Asst. Leader)

19. Susana Pacaldo
20. Loli Edra
21. Fely Bautista
22. Rosa Deocariza
23. Monette Mercurio
24. Judith Fabin
25. Sylvia Ecubeza
26. Ersil Bistoyong
27. Babyluz Patambag

28. Rowena Corpuz
29. Jeanne Lanza
30. Emelyn Bartolome
31. Marilou Dela Paz
32. Lee Prudente
33. Marysal Rosario
34. Cecilia Aviar
35. Rosalie Camua
36. Helen Battad
37. Maricel Lucero
38. Darivit Delizo

PALMA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL – Under Team HO – Team Leaders: Aileen G.(events)/Bojie De Leon (infra)/Cody Tambis(infra)

39. Mrs. Rosemarie P. Visaya - Principal
40. Mrs. Cressida Villapando - Librarian
41. Mrs. Ronald Candela - English Master Teacher
42. Mrs. Marianne Vasquez - Gr. 1 Master Teacher
43. Ms. Mamiya Natividad - GT1 Teacher
44. Aurora Cervano
45. Esperanza Dela Cruz
46. Irene Vivian Villegas
47. Aiko Cantones

Amway employees:

48. Mike Vallente - Operations
49. Jenn Diaz - Operations
50. Grace Mogol – Operations/host
51. Christine Michelle Reyes – Tech Reg
52. Diana Litonjua – Training
53. Maritess Pagaduan - Marketing
54. Michelle Ochoa – facilitator
55. Lourdes Jaynos – Finance

(please email me if you want to join, thanks! Davao leg is on Feb, and Cebu and CDO TBA in 2016)

For the auction updates: Here are the successful bids.

24-Oct	OLIVIA FERNANDEZ	49	1200
24-Oct	OLIVIA FERNANDEZ	11	1000

24-Oct	LOREILYNN RAFIL	50	1000
23-Oct	QINGXIN ZUO	36	500
23-Oct	GRACE MOGOL	21	750
23-Oct	ROMANO AQUINO	56	600
28-Oct	JM FEDERICO	41	800
30-Oct	MICHELLE OCHOA	24	1000
26-Oct	CHRISTINE GRACE TRIA	13	500
30-Oct	JOHN MICHAEL ROBINAS	74	500
30-Oct	MICHAEL DELACRUZ	14	1500
30-Oct	HANY LOU MAGPANTAY	46	500
30-Oct	HANY LOU MAGPANTAY	19	500
30-Oct	MARIA LUISA ARCEO	29	500
30-Oct	PATERNA GEALON	38	1,000
3-Nov	ABO MICHAEL JOHN HILARIO	69	1,000
3-Nov	ENDIAN LI	16	500
3-Nov	AI LI ZHANG	22	1,000
9-Nov	AU SHEN MIN	30	3500

Michelle Punongbayan- Ochoa

Corporate Affairs and Executive Officer | Office of the Country Manager

Feliza Bldg. G/F 108 Rufino St., corner Dela Rosa Legaspi Village, Makati City

T: +632-8148181 ext 1802 | F: +632-8927909(DL/telefax)

Michelle.ochoa@amway.com +639178898181

(Attachments: Auction Invite and Storytelling Poster)

You are invited!
Storytelling Basics and Beyond
A Workshop with Museo Pambata

November 13, 2015

9am to 2pm

Amway Makati Head Office Training Room

Identify best practices in telling stories and facilitating learning sessions.
Improve existing modules and methods of storytelling including interactive shadowplay and puppetry
Plan out creative and thematic activities around books and reading

Learn How to Tell Stories and Styles

Includes Storytelling Demos and Processing Tips in small groups
Planning and Evaluation for Storytelling Sessions

RSVP on or before October 30:
ABOs c/o Mike Valiente for Mandaluyong Volunteers (571-7162) a
nd Hany Magpantay/Jenn Diaz for Makati Volunteers (840-2228/89305730)
Employees: c/o Michelle Ochoa (8148181 LOCAL 1802/09178898181) michelle.ochoa@amway.com

Email 3:

Announcement Using DevCom Practice - Sharing Research Statistics and

Defining the Development Problematique:

- **Conversational**
- **Positive Approach**
- **Statistics and Scientific Approach**
- **Use of ICTs (Intranet, Internet, Computer based communication, microsites, links, and online resources.)**
- **Non-formal and goal focused**
- **Visual aid includes a photograph of children in depressed areas.**

From: Michelle Ochoa

Sent: Tuesday, April 12, 2016 6:15 PM

To: PHL.All.Staff <PHL.All.Staff@amway.com>

Subject: One by One Calendar Updates May to June Activities

Dear **CSR Champions**,

We are happy to share with you our calendar updates for One by One Campaign this May. Included in the calendar are: (1) Davao Storytelling Training, and (2) the Outreach Program that we sponsored for Street Children in Manila, both in partnership with Museo Pambata. I will update you should there be any change in the details/date.

See our latest calendar in this link: [One by One Global Force for Good Calendar – May to June 2016](#)

Or click here to view shared folder files with the latest calendar (intranet): [One by One Shared Folder](#)

For the outreach program dates, these are all Saturdays and we can SHARE preloved clothes, food, books, school supplies to the kids (there are around 35 kids ages 7 to 14). Museo has opened their doors to our volunteers (Employees and ABOs). Volunteers may register through email (michelle.choa@amway.com) or through enlisting at ADC Makati or ADC Mandaluyong. Dates are May 21, May 28 and June 4 respectively . Time is 9am to 12 noon and the venue is at Museo Pambata. ***We will do a 30 minute storytelling activity and provide healthy snacks for the kids during the outreach dates.***

Children remain the most vulnerable members of our society and are exposed to various threats like hunger, deprivation of basic needs (food, water, shelter), lack of education. In the Philippines, approximately 40 percent of our population comprise of children (2010 data, roughly 36.6M) aged below 18. Out of this, an estimated 1.5M children were identified as living in the streets, and an estimated total of 22,728 of which are in Luzon alone. Despite the reported economic growth, poverty remains a culprit why millions of children are still exposed to the harshness of life.

Sources/for Further Reading:

http://www.unicef.org/philippines/reallives_11786.html

<http://www.rappler.com/move-ph/101644-psychological-poverty-children-philippines>

http://www.unicef.org/philippines/brief05_fnl.pdf

<http://dirp3.pids.gov.ph/webportal/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1433.pdf>

Let's join hands to HELP children various communities near us and experience REAL LIFE changing experiences through our advocacy, One by One Campaign – Global Force for Good! Happy volunteering and make your hours count!

“If we won't help, then who will. If not today, then when? There is power in making NOW happen.”

P.S.

We will update you with Manila, Cebu and CDO activities at our beneficiary schools. We will only do product donation for Brigada in Highway Hills and Benitez Elementary School (More details soon!.)

Warm regards,

Michelle Punongbayan- Ochoa

**Corporate Affairs and Executive Officer | Office of the Country
Manager**

Feliza Bldg. G/F 108 Rufino St., corner Dela Rosa Legaspi Village, Makati
City

T: +632-8148181 ext 1802 | F: +632-8927909(DL/telefax)

Michelle.ochoa@amway.com +639178898181

Email 4 - Announcement About the Goals and Objectives.

- **Conversational but with a serious tone regarding the development problem addressed.**
- **Devcom approach - scientific data and statistics presented**
- **Illustrates the alignment between the local campaign and the global campaign**
- **Promotes ownership of the campaign through the CSR Campaign Shirt (Uniform for the campaign).**
- **Making the CSR Journey Map attainable through donation of books in lieu of volunteer hours (this works for those employees and distributors who are busy and travels most of the time.**
- **Management is copied to increase confidence and transparency, boost employee morale, encourage action and visibility of key supporters and participants**

From: Michelle Ochoa

Sent: Thursday, September 08, 2016 4:31 PM

To: PHL.All.Staff

Cc: Maria Elenita Olmedo; Boon Wang Leo

Subject: "Be the Change In Your Community" - One by One CSR Updates for September to December 2016

Dear **CSR Champions**,

We are happy to share that your new CSR Shirt and Cap bearing our new CSR battle cry “**Be The Change in Your Community**” will be available next week at Head Office and may likewise be requested by teams in NCR Based + Cebu ADCs from the CW. Volunteering has always been a core practice and is a special culture close to our hearts as Amway employees. Since 2003, when One by One Campaign was launched globally, affiliate offices have established their own flagship programs in their own markets to sustain this promise of Helping People Live Better Lives. Here is an update below on our CSR initiatives from a global and affiliate perspective.

Championing Sustainable Development Goals SDG 2 and SDG4

- Globally, our fight against malnutrition through the Power of 5 initiative addresses in part SGD 2 (Zero Hunger) and on affiliate level, we are striving to address SDG4 (Quality Education). See below our Global CSR 2016 Goals and Accomplishments for this campaign against Malnutrition and Hunger.

- **Source:** <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs>

2016 Goals and Accomplishments

Provide 5 million Nutrilite Little Bits in 2016

- In 15 countries by end of year
- Achieved 5MM Little Bits goal,
- Will be supporting more than 30,000 children

Expanding Nutrilite Power of 5 Campaign

- Continue to leverage the malnutrition mapping research
- Raised more than \$8 MM in partnership with Affiliates and ABOs

Positioning ABOs as societal value creators through the Nutrilite Power of 5 Leadership Circle.

- Nutrilite Power of 5 Leadership Circle membership has increased from 71 leaders to 98
- On track to support at least 10 LC members activities by end of year
- Provide unique Power of 5 experiences to at least 12 ABO leaders

PHL Literacy Campaign Through Storytelling

- In the Philippines, we started our campaign in 2004 and launched our first initiative in 2005, based on a “Literacy Campaign Through Storytelling” program. We adopted our first Library under the Department of Education’s “Adopt-A- School” Program (F. Benitez

Elementary School, Makati), and since then we have helped renovate and **built 7 libraries nationwide** in locations close to Amway ADCs. All our projects are managed by our employees / various ADC based CSR teams.

Our Nutrilite Runs (**then 1K Run in 2011**) funded the library projects annually. Feel proud that you are all part of this collaborative effort to educate children and reach communities. As a tradition in APHL, we ourselves donate volunteer hours and this year we will aim for 13 hours until March 2017 as a pledge for the 13 years of volunteerism across our organization.

Please see attached calendar announcement and October Freedom Friday sponsorship (TBA on details soon) on how our ABOs can also participate and support our activities. Book donations are still accepted and will be considered as volunteer hours (1 new book = 1 hour; 3 Books = 1 milestone/activity point). We will award the first batch of 13 Hour Champions on December (staff) and all ABOs during Freedom Fridays (as they complete it). Meanwhile, we will update you on specific dates for the 2nd leg of our nationwide Storytelling Caravan based on our ADC Team's availability. We will update you once the online registration form is up at our CSR microsite.

Please save the date on December 10, Saturday, 9am to 12 noon as we again help the less fortunate homeless children of "Luneta" during our special Christmas Outreach. You may donate clothes, food, toys for this. Please email me if you are interested to help. Let us all become the much needed "CHANGE" in our community and the world! **Thank you and Happy Volunteering!**

P.S.

Good News! Please see attached revised CSR toolkit p. 11 which indicates Philippines Market as one of the benchmarks for best practices in CSR. Kudos to all of you!

Warm regards,

Michelle Punongbayan – Ochoa

Corporate Affairs and Executive Officer | Office of the Country Manager

Feliza Bldg. G/F 108 Rufino St., corner Dela Rosa Legaspi Village, Makati City

T: +632-8148181 ext 1802 | F: +632-8927909(DL/telefax)

Michelle.ochoa@amway.com +639178898181

Email 4 - Celebrating the Victory of Teams and the Value of Collaboration

- **Conversational**
- **Highlight Leadership Roles**
- **Sharing the perspective of participants**
- **Sharing of best practices in CSR implementations**
- **Shows sustainability as a quality of the campaign (announcement of succeeding activity in another location)**

From: Michelle Ochoa

Sent: Tuesday, October 18, 2016 9:19 AM

To: PHL.All.Staff <PHL.All.Staff@amway.com>

Cc: Maria Elenita Olmedo <leni.olmedo@Amway.com>; Boon Wang Leo <Leo_Boon_Wang@Amway.com>

Subject: Fw: Davao CSR Activity at Lacson

Dear CSR Champions,

Let us all congratulate **ADC Davao Team** for their successful roll out of the One by One Storytelling Caravan and Reading Project for students of Lacson Elementary School, Calinan Davao. Sharing across the report and photos from our **Team Leader, Santiago Tambis** who passionately leads his team to **Be the Change in their Community**.

E-mail details below from Santi:

"Our story telling last Thursday is successful. Teachers are showcasing their learnings from Museo Pambata workshop as well as our team in delivering a wonderful story to the students. We are grateful to see that the students are very attentive and interested to hear the stories. It was another achievement to know that students learned and enjoyed the activity.

We also gave token of appreciation to our participants, esp. teachers. (OBO mug & carnival)

Participants:

- 1.) 6 Lacson Teachers headed by Principal Elizabeth Ayag.
- 2.) Amway Staff - role playing
 - Santi
 - Megazar
 - Regine
 - Roland
 - Renie - Readyman
 - Darrel - eSpring Tech
 - Artess - Nutritionist
- 3.) 35 Grade 1 students (Non Readers) & 5 parents "

Are you ready to be the change in your communities? Today CDO is having their activity at South City Central School on Friday with Karen Escartin heading the team. Meanwhile we will be at Highway Hills Integrated Elementary School under the leadership of Mike Vallente. Join us as more activities unfold, join hands with us in bringing change in places where it is needed. Be a Star Volunteer in your community and document your journey! Happy Volunteering everyone!

Warm regards,
Michelle

C. 1K Run Posters

<http://www.marathonphilippines.com/tag/amway-1k-run/>

Registration Fee: P350.00
Includes: Start, Bib & Car Sticker
To qualify, please visit our Facebook page.

BIB No:

Registration Period:

JAN 24	FEB 14	FEB 21
<small>START</small>	<small>START</small>	<small>START</small>

PARTICIPANT'S INFORMATION

LAST NAME: FIRST NAME: M.A.:

CONTACT NUMBERS (Mobile or Landline No.): ADD (Home/Office):
 YES NO

HOME ADDRESS:

EMAIL ADDRESS: BIRTH DATE:

AGE: GENDER: SHIRT SIZE:

WAVEN
 I hereby declare that all information I have provided above are true and correct. Therefore, I am eligible for all rules and regulations set forth for the "Nutralite Health Run". As such, I am aware that as participant of this activity, I acknowledge all the risks, personal injury, illness and even death which may result from my participation. I agree to release and indemnify Nutralite Health Run, Marathon Philippines and its affiliates, its organizers and sponsors from any damages and liabilities which may occur or be claimed against it in connection with my participation in this activity. I further certify that I am of legal age, I will attend on qualified consent. Furthermore, I hereby state that I voluntarily entered as a participant and assumed complete responsibility that I am physically fit to participate in this activity. Hence, I voluntarily waive this waiver and I agree to hold and understand its contents and consequences thereon.

Participant's Signature/Guardian's Signature: _____ Date: _____

Yes! I consent to furnish my personal information and other details indicated above to be part of Amway Philippines database program. I authorize Amway Philippines to use my personal information as indicated above for the purpose of this mail only. I consent to receive communication and product updates from Amway Philippines.

#AmwayHappydings

January 24, 2016
Old World of Asia Grounds, Pasig City

February 14, 2016
ADC CDO (Pala Community Center, Bantay, Old Agulayan Road, Bantay, Cebu City)

February 21, 2016
ADC Cebu (Pala Community Center, Bantay, Old Agulayan Road, Bantay, Cebu City)

Join now and avail these promos!

5x1 Runners Promo
Get 5x1 (5 Nutralite Health Run Runs 99 for 199) when you register together. **499 and 199 (5) Starts (999 or More Starts)**.
Maximum 500 registrations per group.

Double X Double Up Promo
Get 2x1 (2 Nutralite Health Run Runs 99 for 199) when you register. **499 and 199 (2) Starts (999 or More Starts)**.
Maximum 500 registrations per group.

Save Parties will get:
 • FREE Sign-up kit (see below)
 • Race Bib
 • Nutralite Running Bag
 • Race Kit
 • FREE QR Function for App location

Gifts Prizes:
 • FREE product samples
 • 1st-3rd Place
 • 1st-3rd Place
 • Cash Prizes

Don't Miss!
 Join Nutralite Health Run today and enjoy gift to yourself. Get a special gift certificate if you finish 5 runs. You will be invited to receive this by the Nutralite Philippines system.
 Includes 1000 Nutralite Health Run Runs, 1000 Nutralite Health Run Starts, and 1000 Nutralite Health Run Starts.

bodykey **ARTOTEX** **more** **isore** **network** **glister** **www** **ACHIEVERS**

Facebook Twitter LinkedIn YouTube

NUTRILITE™

HEALTH RUN

1K, 5K & 10K
Registration Fee:
₱250
Includes: Shirt & Bib

21K
Registration Fee:
₱850
Includes: Shirt & Bib

October 15, 2017
SM Mall of Asia Grounds, Pasay City

October 29, 2017
SM Ecoland, Matina, Davao City

November 5, 2017
Centrio Mall, CDO

Join now and avail this promo!
Get ONE (1) Nutrilite™ Acerola C for FREE when you register
FIVE (5) non-ABOs to join the race!*

★ ★ ★
First 21K Finisher who
crosses the Finish Line will
get **PhP 10,000** cash prize!

Race Finisher will get:

- FREE Sign-up (non-ABOs only)
- Nutrilite™ Drawstring Bag
- Nutrilite™ Pen
- P500 Gift Voucher (ABO only)
- Finisher Shirt & Medal (21K Finishers only)

Raffle Prizes:

- Php 10,000 Cash Prize
- Php 10,000 Gift Voucher
- Go Pro Hero 4 Silver
- iPad Mini
- iPod Touch
- Amway Gift Packs

Join Nutrilite Health Run today and help gift a child with a good book tomorrow. A portion of your registration will be donated to Amway One by One Campaign for Children. So be part of the Nutrilite Health Run and help a child read his way to a brighter future.

ARTISTRY eSpring SATINIQUE G&H glister home APSA-80 ACHIEVERS M.Y.U

OfficialAmwayPH @AmwayOfficialPH amwayph_official | www.amway.com.ph • call us: #AMWAY (#26929)

Per DOH FDA CFR PERMIT NO. 0735 L. 2017

APPENDIX I

Social Media and Web Based Links

A. Media Coverage for One by One - Articles About the Local Campaign

<http://manilastandard.net/mobile/article/144880>

<https://www.amway.com.ph/ph/amway-global/csr/one-by-one>

<http://www.philstar.com/nation/22595/one-one-campaign-children-launched>

<http://www.entrepreneur.com.ph/business-ideas/one-by-one-campaign-for-children-changes-life-transforms-futures-esupplier>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bkEwYbo0d8M>

Outreach in Smokey Mountain, Tondo Manila with Philippine Christian Foundation :
Book Donation Drive

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1pqVV6Q3JZs> Child leads opening prayer

Outreach in Davao, Baganga after Storm Pablo

<http://3blmedia.com/News/CSR/Amway-Philippines-Demonstrates-Award-Winning-%E2%80%9CBayanihan%E2%80%9D-Spirit-Sense-Community-or>

<http://www.dugout.ph/2017/08/amway-partners-with-runrio-for-nutrilite-run.html>

By Ivan Saldajeno

MAKATI--For the fifth time, Amway will organize the Nutrilite Health Run as officially launched on Wednesday at The Plantation Restaurant.

The 21-kilometer race will happen on Oct. 15 at the SM Mall of Asia Concert Grounds in Pasay.

The Pasay leg will also run through the cities of Manila and Parañaque with Roxas Boulevard as the main road.

A 10K, 5K, and 1K sprint race will also take place there.

To promote competitiveness, Amway and its partner for this event, RunRio, will give PHP20,000 to the ultimate top finisher of the 21K run and PHP10,000 for the ultimate top 10K finisher.

RunRio president Rio Dela Cruz, however, clarified that there will still be prizes for the top three finishers for each gender. All 21K racers who will finish the race within four hours will receive a finisher shirt and medal each.

Another leg will happen at the SM Ecoland in Davao City on Oct. 29

For the participants to further prepare for the race, a free running clinic will take place twice a week leading to race day.

Dela Cruz will himself conduct the Makati leg of the clinic every Monday and Wednesday at the Ayala Triangle Garden, while a separate clinic for the Davaoneño runners will happen every Tuesday and Thursday.

Registration is now underway online at amway.com.ph and at runrio.com and offline at the Amway Distribution Centers here, in Cagayan De Oro, in Cebu, and in Davao. Separate registration booths will be put up at selected Toby's Sports stores in Metro Manila starting Aug. 28.

Proceeds will go to Amway's "One By One Campaign for Children" book donation drive.

Follow him on Twitter: [@IvanSaldajeno](https://twitter.com/IvanSaldajeno)

D. Facebook Advertorials for the Annual Health Run

APPENDIX J

Industry CSR Photos to show that Amway also participates at industry level.

a) HADSAP

In 2015, Amway took part in a donation drive for SOS Village in Paranaque organized by The Health and Dietary Supplement Association of the Philippines.

b) DSAP

Amway participated in the Direct Selling Association of the Philippines CSR Campaign in 2016.

c) AMCHAM Philippines

Amway also supported the annual American Chamber of the Philippines CSR, Honor Your Secretary Day and Amcham Charity Ball.

d) Red Cross Philippines Donations (insert photo)

Total Donation of Php 4M or 100,000 USD from Amway Global

H. Video links for One by One Campaign

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fWre7FrJKV0>

FW: Follow up of ASP data and stats for research work

People

[Michelle Ochoa <michelle.choa@Amway.com>](mailto:michelle.choa@Amway.com)

To

'michelle.choa@upou.edu.ph' 'michellechoa73@yahoo.com'

07/01/15 at 1:01 AM

Data on ASP

From: dalen esmeralda [<mailto:aspprogram.center@gmail.com>]

Sent: Wednesday, July 01, 2015 12:45 PM

To: Michelle Ochoa

Subject: Re: Follow up of ASP data and stats for research work

Hi Ms. Michelle,

Sorry for the late reply. I hope this will help you.

Godbless!

dalen

On Mon, Jun 29, 2015 at 4:57 PM, Michelle Ochoa <michelle.choa@amway.com> wrote:

Hi Ms. Dalen,

Hope this email finds you well. I would like to follow up if there is an update on the data I am requesting for my research. This will be greatly appreciated, thanks.

Regards,

Michelle

--

Thank you!

Dalen C. Esmeralda
 Resource Mobilization Officer
 Adopt-A-School Program

5/F Bonifacio Bldg., DepEd Complex
 Meralco Ave., Pasig City
 Tel. Nos. (02) 638 8637 or 39

aspprogram.center@gmail.com

APPENDIX K

Survey Link:

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/H6CWJCV>

Names of Employees:

1. Rizabelle Santiago - Employee, Finance Team
2. Christine Grace Tria - Management, Communications Team
3. Jenn Edlynn Diaz - Team Leader, Mandaluyong area
4. Santiago Tambis - Team Leader Davao Area
5. Joy Marie Bacay - Volunteer, Product Marketer
6. John Joseph Barbara - Volunteer, IT Department
7. Christine Michelle Reyes - Management, Volunteer
8. Norie Christie Esgasane - Team Leader, Davao and Makati Area
9. Hany Lou Magpantay - Team Leader, Cebu and Makati Area
10. Bojie Valencia De Leon - Team Leader, Team Urdaneta and Makati

Questionnaire:

Q1 How effectively was the campaign message communicated to you?

Totals : 80% - very effectively 20% Effectively

What was the most used communication channel for the campaign project announcement?

1. Email - 20%
2. Printed posters - 0%
3. Via company blog, social media content - 30%
4. Combination of these - 50%

Q3 - Did the CSR Project Officer communicate proactively before and after the implementation?

Yes- 100%

No - 0%

Q4 - Are you an active participant in the CSR campaign?

Yes - 80%

No - 20%

Q5 - Are the campaign objectives aligned with the company's values?

Yes - 100%

No - 0%

Q6 - Do you think that the company helps its beneficiaries improve their lives and conditions?

Yes- 100%

Q7 - Do you want to participate in this campaign again if given a chance?

Yes 100%

Q8 - Are you proud to be part of this campaign?

Yes - 90% response

Follow up Question: How did it help you personally? 1 Response

It has opened my eyes to the joint responsibility of private persons and the government in addressing social problems like lack of resources for education.

Phase 2 FGD: Interview Questionnaire for Partner Stakeholders: Result:

Questions:

1. How has the campaign impacted your life?

- a) Slightly
- b) Moderately
- c) Strongly

Please elaborate why.

2. Describe the activity that has created a strong impact in your perception of how Amway has helped society in general? (State an activity, e.g. storytelling, outreach, relief drive etc.)

3. Do you feel that the partner is equipped and supported by the company when you roll out the campaign activities?
4. Do you think that the activities achieve the objective of helping people?
5. What are the existing and possible challenges that you feel are commonly faced in sustaining a partnership with the government?

Answers:

Viva Carreon - Project Coordinator and Teacher at Highway Hills Integrated school

Questions:

2. How has the campaign impacted your life?

- a) Slightly
- b) Moderately
- c) Strongly

Please elaborate why.

Because I feel touched by the company's effort to provide resources to the school.

2. Describe the activity that has created a strong impact in your perception of how Amway has helped society in general? (State an activity, e.g. storytelling, outreach, relief drive etc.) Answer: Storytelling - because it develops the reading interest of the students. And the Brigada Eskwela, because the company provides cleaning materials without asking for contribution from the parents.

3. Do you feel that the partner is equipped and supported by the company when you roll out the campaign activities? Answer: Yes

4. Do you think that the activities achieve the objective of helping people? Answer: Yes

5. What are the existing and possible challenges that you feel are commonly faced in sustaining a partnership with the government? Answer: None

Charls Arisgado, Assistant Principal of Francisco Benitez Elementary School:

1. How has the campaign impacted your life?

C. strongly

Please elaborate why? The company serves as an inspiration and gives hope to the school children whenever support and service given to the different activities of the school is rendered.

2. Describe the activity has created a strong impact in your perception of How Amway has helped society in general? (State an activity, e.g. storytelling, outreach, relief operations, et. al and when it happened)

Some programs of the school like storytelling, poster making contest and Brigada Eskwela which are yearly done is being supported by the Amway. Every time the Amway supports the school activities, it helps to create a quality education of the community. Thus, Amway helps produce a productive citizen.

3. Do you feel that the partner is equipped and supported by the company when you roll out the campaign activities?

To make the partnership effective there should be a monitoring, Survey and evaluation in every action done. (The answer to this is yes, Amway is monitoring it but sometimes there is a challenge in getting feed back. Perhaps the

response was a call to do direct monitoring which is the job of the school coordinator/librarian in charge as to frequency of their own storytelling activities. Amway is only required to roll out two to three major visits annually per MOU agreements)

4. Do you feel that the activities achieve the objective of helping people?

Yes.

5. What are the possible negative effects or challenges that you feel are commonly faced in sustaining the partnership (considering it is a PPP or Public Private Partnership with the government)?

“In my opinion, sometimes the service, support or donation is not rendered or given directly to the school populace.”

(Researcher’s notes : Further inquiry revealed that there could be a misconception about the lessening of activities in this particular beneficiary as their library which was the area used for the storytelling campaign was moved to a temporary area during a stopped construction in the wake of Mayor Binay’s case. Also, the company decided to focus more activities in provincial based schools where help was needed (e.g. Davao, Tacloban areas) and in Manila (Rafael Palma Elementary which was close to depressed areas.) A case of changed priorities but still within the MOU agreement and budget.

John Michael Federico - HR Manager, Amway Philippines

Survey:

1. How has the campaign impacted your life?

a. slightly

b. moderately

c. strongly

Please elaborate why? Changed my life in a way that I become more aware about the needs of our students on education through literacy.

2. Describe the activity has created a strong impact in your perception of how your company has helped society in general? - **Storytelling.**

(State an activity, e.g. storytelling, outreach, relief operations, et. al and when it happened)

3. Do you feel equipped and supported by the company when you roll out the campaign activities? – **OF COURSE!**

4. Do you feel that the activities achieve the objective of helping people? – **BIG YES!**

5. What are the possible negative effects, or challenges that you feel are commonly faced in sustaining the partnership (considering it is a PPP or Public Private Partnership with the government)? – **Change of government or policies in the Dep. Of Education which might impact the partnership of private and public entities. And also change in leadership and direction of both entities.**

Santiago Tambis - Amway Distribution Center Supervisor, Davao City

1. How has the campaign impacted your life?

c. Strongly, it makes me feel responsible and proud that I may somehow part of helping the community.

Please elaborate why? (no response)

2. Describe the activity has created a strong impact in your perception of how your company has helped society in general? (State an activity, e.g. storytelling, outreach, relief operations, et. al and when it happened)

“First is the relief operations after typhoon Pablo hits Mindanao – it was back December 2012. Second, is the reading program for Lacson Elem School.”

3. Do you feel equipped and supported by the company when you roll out the campaign activities?

Yes! Amway provide workshop in partnership with Museo Pambata

4. Do you feel that the activities achieve the objective of helping people?

Yes!

5. What are the possible negative effects, or challenges that you feel are commonly faced in sustaining the partnership (considering it is a PPP or Public Private Partnership with the government)? Corruption and misuse of funds.

Worldview Survey of C4D for CSR implementation:

https://www.researchgate.net/post/How_does_communication_C4D_help_in_strengthening_Corporate_Social_Responsibility_projects_that_lead_to_development_of_individuals_and_communities

How does communication (C4D) help in strengthening Corporate Social Responsibility projects that lead to development of individuals and communities?

How can CSR transcend from a company propelled activity into an act of social responsibility?

How extensively is communication used to achieve the objectives of both the sponsor company/organization and their beneficiary/beneficiaries?

Are we responsible as private citizens / private companies to help the government uplift the lives of the underprivileged and the underdeveloped communities?

Does CSR in Southeast Asia accomplish the same effects as it does in a first world country? (e.g. during calamities, and economic recession?)

Ongoing Survey on C4D in CSR at Research Gate:

